

ANNEX I

Glossary

Language influences how we perceive the world and how we think about and communicate transformative change. It also influences the actions that we take, as well as those that we overlook or fail to take. However, there is no one-language-fits-all approach to understanding and activating transformative change. Many important qualities and characteristics of biodiversity and human-nature relationships are not captured in the English language (Harrison, 2008). For example, many Indigenous languages refer to the natural world through expressions, metaphors and concepts that capture the complex flow and interdependence of life (Salmón, 2000). Of the more than 7,000 languages spoken around the world today, an estimated 3,000 (43 per cent) are endangered (*Endangered Languages Project*, n.d.). The period between 2022-2032 has been declared the International Decade of Indigenous Languages, which among other objectives aims for constitutional and legal recognition, preservation and revitalization of Indigenous languages (*International Decade of Indigenous Languages 2022 – 2032 | United Nations For Indigenous Peoples*, n.d.). Recognizing the strong relationship between language diversity and biodiversity (Gorenflo *et al.*, 2012), as well as the importance of a pluralistic understanding of transformative change (**Chapter 1, Box 1.5**), this glossary includes words and concepts from diverse languages that are referred to in the assessment. Recognising that there are several definitions for each term, the glossary reflects a balance between being comprehensive and focused. The definitions provided are not universal; they are related to the context of the Transformative Change Assessment.

A

Accountability: Refers to a willingness to accept responsibility or to account for one's actions. Accountability is related to notions of responsibility, with the two terms often used interchangeably (Biermann & Gupta, 2011; Mason, 2008).

Active disruption: Deliberative efforts to elicit and trigger destabilization or removal of one or more barriers and their related challenges resulting in long-term change in a part or whole system level of infrastructures, markets, regulations, actors and networks, practices, behaviours and views towards biodiversity restoration and living in harmony with nature (Kivimaa *et al.*, 2021).

Actors: Refers to entities such as individuals, organizations, or States that have interests and preferences, decision-making capacities, and strategies (Hasse, 2019). In this assessment, 17 types of actor groups are recognized, organized in four sectors: 1) civil society (civil society organizations, environmental movements/activists, Indigenous Peoples, individual citizens, local communities, non-governmental organizations); 2) private sector (business, donor/foundations, financial actors); 3) government sector (intergovernmental organizations, justice system, local/regional government) and; 4) communication and knowledge sector (education, media and communication, networks, scientific community).

Adaptation: Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities (IPBES, 2021).

Adaptive capacity: The general ability of institutions, systems and individuals to adjust to potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or to cope with the consequences (IPBES, 2021).

Adaptive governance: Includes a range of interactions between actors, networks, organizations, and institutions emerging in pursuit of a desired state for social-ecological systems. It goes beyond top-down processes and explicitly requires processes of participatory co-evaluation and bottom-up evaluation, and responds to the uncertainties and complexities associated with global environmental change (Chaffin *et al.*, 2014).

Adaptive learning: Engagement in ongoing processes of evaluation, learning and adaptation, which allow for contestation, attentive care towards unfolding impacts and mitigation of unintended consequences (Barth *et al.*, 2023).

Agency: The capacity of individual and collective actors to change the course of events or the outcome of processes (Otto *et al.*, 2020). For transformative change, agency can be exercised through a range of roles with individuals working to enact change within their own spheres

of influence. Agency can also apply to non-human entities (Watts, 2013). In this assessment, agency is recognized as something that can be created, shaped and constrained by political-economic processes, cultural and social norms, dominant system paradigms and education and knowledge systems (**Chapter 3**).

Agroecology: The science and practice of applying ecological concepts, principles and knowledge (i.e., the interactions of and explanations for, the diversity, abundance and activities of organisms) to the study, design and management of sustainable agroecosystems. It includes the roles of human beings as a central organism by way of social and economic processes in farming systems. Agroecology examines the roles and interactions among all relevant biophysical, technical and socioeconomic components of farming systems and their surrounding landscapes (IPBES, 2019a). In this assessment, agroecology bridges local traditional and global scientific knowledge through a dialogue of wisdoms, fostering innovation and adaptation of technologies that rely on biodiversity (Gliessman & Titonell, 2015).

Ahimsā: Principle of non-violence in the context of a cosmology where “all lives are integrated and to harm other is to hurt the community as a whole” (Singh, 2014). Origin: India.

Anthropocentrism: The ethical belief that humans alone possess intrinsic value (Goralnik & Nelson, 2012).

Ayni: Refers to how things get in balance or out of balance in the cycle of life. Even though it is often translated into reciprocity in English, the word *ayni* carries a much broader meaning (IPBES, 2019b). Origin: the Andes.

B

Barrier: A manifestation of a challenge in and/or across contexts; a barrier can be an entry point to deal with a challenge (**Chapter 4**).

Birgejupmi: A concept that means ‘to have a good life according to what one has access to’, living in a modest way with interactions between humans and non-humans based on care and respect (Rybråten *et al.*, 2024). Origin: North-Sámi.

Biocapacity: The capacity of a country, a region, or the world, to produce useful biological materials for its human population and to absorb waste materials (IPBES, 2021).

Biocultural diversity: The diversity of life in all its manifestations: biological, cultural and linguistic — which are interrelated (and possibly coevolved) within complex socio-ecological systems (Maffi, 2007).

Biodiversity: The variability among living organisms from all sources including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are a part. This includes variation in genetic, phenotypic, phylogenetic and functional attributes, as well as changes in abundance and distribution over time and space within and among species, biological communities and ecosystems (IPBES, 2021).

Biodiversity conservation: The management of human interactions with genes, species and ecosystems so as to provide the maximum benefit to the present generation while maintaining their potential to meet the needs and aspirations of future generations; encompasses elements of saving, studying and using biodiversity (IPBES, 2019a).

Biodiversity offsets: Measurable conservation outcomes resulting from

actions designed to compensate for significant residual adverse biodiversity impacts arising from project development (Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme, 2012).

Bioeconomy: Refers to economic approaches that harness the potential of biological resources, processes and principles to generate sustainable economic growth, enhance resource efficiency and promote environmental and social well-being (Tan & Lamers, 2021).

Buen Vivir (Sumak Kawsay in Quechua, Suma Qamaña in Aymara): An alternative to economic development-centred approaches, generally defined as forming part of the Andean Indigenous cosmology, based on the belief that true wellbeing is only possible as part of a community in a broad sense, including people, nature and the Earth, linked by mutual responsibilities and obligations and that the wellbeing of the community is above that of the individual (IPBES, 2021).

Business-as-usual: An expression describing a baseline scenario that examines the consequences of continuing current trends in population, economy, technology and human behaviour. Often used as a synonym for status quo (European Environment Agency, n.d.).

C

Capitalism: A configuration of society based on an economic logic that includes the following key elements: 1) the pursuit of profit and its private appropriation, 2) free enterprise and the competitive market, 3) wage labour and the production of commodities, 4) property rights, 5) the financial infrastructure of money and investment that makes possible credit and debt, 6) a highly variable degree of State regulation and 7) a propensity for growth as the productive re-investment of profit. Despite the significant transformation in capitalism historically, the dynamic of profit remains a prime shaper of society (Harris & Delanty, 2023).

Challenge: Something that involves great effort to be done successfully. In this assessment, it refers to situations and/or issues that impede or prevent transformative change, either by exacerbating the difficulties inherent in transformation or introducing new or intentional obstacles to

change. Challenges embody what people think and feel (views and values), what people do (practices) and how society is organized (structures) and they can be manifested in a multitude of ways across contexts (see **Chapter 4**).

Circular economy: A regenerative system in which resource input and waste, emission and energy leakage are minimized by slowing, closing and narrowing material and energy loops. This can be achieved through long-lasting design, maintenance, repair, reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing and recycling (IPBES, 2021).

Clean technology: A procedural approach or method that promotes sustainable development for companies, emphasising that all production phases be addressed such that environmental risks are minimized and underlain by the philosophies of eco-efficiency and eco-friendliness to enhance competitiveness, social responsibility and organizational sustainability (Brahmana & Kontesa, 2021).

Climate change: As defined in Article 1 of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods (IPBES, 2021).

Co-creation: A collaborative process of creation of knowledge between academic and non-academic actors encompassing the co-design of the problem framing, the co-production of knowledge, the co-implementation and dissemination of results (Hakkarainen *et al.*, 2022; Mauser *et al.*, 2013). Often used interchangeably with co-production of knowledge. Same collaborative multi-actor approaches can be extrapolated to co-creating action and change.

Colonialism: The combination of territorial, juridical, cultural, linguistic, political, mental/epistemic and/or economic domination of one group of people or groups of people by another (external) group of people (Murrey, 2020).

Coloniality: Enduring ways of thinking and pervasive structures and patterns of power, inequality and domination established in different eras of colonialism. These have

continued to shape modern societies in cultural, political and knowledge aspects beyond the end of formal colonial rule, becoming a pervasive force. This includes recognition that the legacies of historic injustices, such as the displacement of Indigenous Peoples and local communities and the disruption of their land management practices, are still present and contribute to today's biodiversity challenges (Deringil, 2003; Quijano, 2007).

Consumerism: The relentless economic pursuit of consumption, based on liberal economic theory that increasing consumption is economically beneficial. It describes the effect of the market economy, advertising and mass media on individuals, creating a 'consumer culture' and 'mass consumption' (Wong & Bridges, 2008).

Co-production: In the context of the IPBES conceptual framework, this is the joint contribution by nature and anthropogenic assets in generating nature's contributions to people (IPBES, 2021). In terms of transformative change, it recognizes the importance of Indigenous and local knowledge systems, or 'Walking on Two Legs', which means including traditional ways of knowing in educational systems, but also allowing innovation and new ways of knowing. Traditional ways of knowing can be included, including value-based practices like ceremonies, festivals, rituals, stories, songs and production practices like hunting, cultivation, gathering (IPBES, 2019a; Reid *et al.*, 2020).

Culture: A commonly accepted definition of culture refers to the system of shared beliefs, values, customs, behaviours and artifacts that the members of society use to cope with their world and with one another and that are transmitted from generation to generation through learning (IPBES, 2021).

D

Degrowth: The premise that economic growth cannot be sustained ad infinitum on a resource constrained planet. Degrowth denies the need for economic growth and demands a deep societal change. It began as an activist movement around 2008 and turned into an academic discipline (IPBES, 2021).

Discourse: A form of language use, public speeches or spoken language and ways of speaking. Can also refer to the ideas

or philosophies propagated by different groups, including who uses language, how, why and when. It also refers to a web of meanings, ideas, interactions, practices expressed or represented in texts (spoken and written, gesture and visual imagery) within institutional everyday settings (Bischooping & Gazso, 2015; Dijk, 1997).

Drivers (direct): Natural and anthropogenic factors or pressures that directly cause changes in nature, anthropogenic assets, nature's contributions to people and a good quality of life. Direct drivers identified in the IPBES Global Assessment include land/sea use change, direct exploitation, climate change, pollution and invasive alien species (IPBES, 2019a, 2021).

Drivers (indirect): Human actions and decisions that affect nature diffusely by altering and influencing direct drivers as well as other indirect drivers. Indirect drivers identified in the IPBES Global Assessment include demographic and sociocultural factors, economic and technological factors, institutional and governance factors and conflicts and epidemics (IPBES, 2019a, 2021).

E

Ecocide: Refers to severe and either widespread or long-term environmental harm that is caused by unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of such harm (Higgins *et al.*, 2013; Lindgren, 2018; Sands *et al.*, 2021).

Ecological civilization: A concept rooted in Chinese traditional wisdom based on the unity of nature and humanity. It has been used to harmonize the apparent contradiction between economic development and environmental protection, including biodiversity conservation (Ma & Wei, 2021).

Ecological crisis: Potential destruction of conditions that sustain human life on Earth owing to exacerbated levels of human interventions; comprises interwoven environmental issues such as global climate change, soil degradation, pollution, toxicity of synthetic chemicals etc. (Takács-Sánta, 2022; Vasan, 2018).

Ecological footprint: An indicator that accounts for human demand on global biological resources. It compares the level of consumption with the available amount

of bioproductive land and sea area and has been designed to show a possible exceedance of this "sustainability threshold" (Wiedmann & Barrett, 2010).

Ecological intensification:

Environmentally friendly replacement of anthropogenic inputs (such as pesticides and fertilisers) while maintaining or enhancing crop productivity, by including regulating and supporting ecosystem services management in agricultural practices (Bommarco *et al.*, 2013).

Ecologically unequal exchange: The theory of ecologically unequal exchange goes beyond monetary flows and explicitly considers flows of materials, energy, labour, water and land embodied in international trade. Ecologically unequal exchange refers to asymmetric net transfers of these resources from peripheral to core areas of the global economic system, which can lead to environmental distribution conflicts (Dorninger *et al.*, 2021; Hornborg, 1998, 2014; Hornborg & Martinez-Alier, 2016).

Eco-social contracts: A social contract incorporating the ecological dimension to achieve sustainable development for all. Eco-social contracts are grounded in a broad consensus between different stakeholders, embarking on a democratic, inclusive and participatory decision-making process at multiple levels and feeding evidence-based policy proposals into decision-making forums, to arrive at a shared vision, concrete objectives and commitments and accountability mechanisms (UNRISD, 2022).

Ecosystem: A dynamic complex of plant, animal and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a functional unit (IPBES, 2021).

Ecosystem-based approaches: A strategy for the integrated management of land, water and living resources that promotes conservation and sustainable use in an equitable way. An ecosystem approach is based on the application of appropriate scientific methods, focused on levels of biological organization that encompass the essential structure, processes, functions and interactions among and between organisms and their environment. It recognizes that humans, with their cultural diversity, are an integral component of many ecosystems (IPBES, 2019a).

Ecosystem services: The benefits people obtain from ecosystems, which include supporting, regulating, provisioning and cultural services (IPBES, 2019a).

Empowerment: The process by which people gain control over the factors and decisions that shape their lives, as well as by which they increase their assets and attributes and build capacities to gain access, partners, networks and/or a voice, in order to gain control (IPBES, 2021).

The process of challenging existing power relations and of gaining greater control over the sources of power may also be termed empowerment (Battilwala, 1994).

Environmental justice: The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, colour, national origin, or income with respect to the development, implementation and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations and policies (Bullard, 2001).

Epistemic community: A network of professionals with recognized expertise and confidence in a particular domain and an authoritative claim to policy relevant knowledge within that domain or issue-area (Haas, 1992).

Epistemology: The study or theory of the nature and grounds of knowledge, with reference to its limits and validity. From the Greek words *episteme* or knowledge, understanding and *logos* or account, argument, reason (Steup & Neta, 2005).

Equality: Refers to similarity in treatment, capacity, participation, or distribution of benefits or harms even as it is evident that these different dimensions of equality connect to different conceptions of justice (Benhabib, 2002; Cook & Hegtvedt, 1983; Dworkin, 2001; Rawls, 2020). The Gini Index, focusing on material endowments, is the most common measure of (in)equality (Alvaredo *et al.*, 2018; Milanovic, 2011).

Equity: Concerns socially informed, ethical evaluations of existing distributions and changes in endowments, benefits and harms. It is closely related to concepts of justice and fairness and often used interchangeably with these concepts in everyday conversations (Cook & Hegtvedt, 1983; Rakowski, 1991; P. Young, 1995). See Justice.

Ethics: Involves questions of justice and value. Justice is concerned with right and wrong, equity and fairness and, in general, with the rights to which people and living beings are entitled. Value is a matter of worth, benefit, or good (IPCC, n.d.). In this assessment, it also refers to a system of accepted beliefs that influence behaviours, especially based on morals (see **Chapter 2**).

Ethics of care: The diverse, dynamic things humans and non-humans do to sustain bodies, selves, environments and worlds. Instead of understanding care as an altruistic, unidirectional act, care is recognized as involving collective, embodied and reciprocal work, in which non-humans (plants, animals, microorganisms, phenomena, infrastructures, physical forces, spiritual entities and technologies) also participate. These ethics and associated practices circulate in and are crucial for the regeneration of the complex webs of earthly life in which humans and non-humans are interdependent (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017).

Etuptmunk: The gift of multiple perspectives; a conceptual framework coined by Mi'kmaw Elder Albert Marshall in 2004 for unifying knowledge systems. It is described as "learning to see from one eye with the strengths of Indigenous knowledges and ways of knowing and from the other eye with the strengths of Western knowledges and ways of knowing and to use both these eyes together, for the benefit of all" (Bartlett *et al.*, 2012). Origin: Mi'kmaw; Eastern Canada.

Extractivism: Appropriation of nature in large amounts chiefly for sale on the export market with little or no transformation, often causing irreversible damage to the environment and dispossession of local communities (EHNE, n.d.).

F

Fairness: Impartial and just treatment without favouritism or discrimination, whereby each person is considered of equal worth with equal opportunity (IPCC, n.d.). A value that is considered integral to the establishment and maintenance of social relations at every level, from the local to the global and from the micro to the macro (Rayner & Malone, 2001).

Feedbacks: A sequence of effects among variables in a system, where a change in

one variable causes changes in others, which then influence the first variable and its effects. Positive feedbacks amplify or reinforce the effect; negative feedbacks dampen or decrease the effect (Rodríguez-González *et al.*, 2020; Walker & Salt, 2012).

Fiction: Something invented through creativity and imagination or assumed to be possible, regardless of its truth. In terms of literature, it includes science fiction, speculative fiction, futures fictional narratives and other genres representing creative approaches to narrating the potential for transformative change (Caira & Schaeffer, 2011).

Food system: Embraces the entire range of actors and their interlinked value-adding activities involved in the production, aggregation, processing, distribution, consumption and disposal of food products that originate from agriculture, forestry or fisheries and food industries and the broader economic, societal and natural environments in which they are embedded (FAO, 2018).

G

Gaga: The Tayal Law - a broad concept that encompasses ways of being and interacting with others and the land (Silan & Munkejord, 2022). Origin: Tayal, Taiwan.

Ganma: Translated as "Two Ways", it describes a dialectical relationship where distinct knowledge systems—like freshwater and saltwater—meet and mix without losing their individual characteristics. *Ganma* represents a method for engaging in meaningful two-way collaborations, emphasising how two opposed patterns of ideas complement, interact and relate to one another in ways that respect and preserve the distinctiveness of each knowledge system (Muller *et al.*, 2012). Origin: Yolngu, Australia.

Global biodiversity financing gap: The difference between the total annual amount of capital currently flowing towards global biodiversity conservation and the total amount of funds needed to sustainably manage biodiversity and maintain ecosystem integrity (Deutz *et al.*, 2020).

Good quality of life: Within the context of the IPBES Conceptual Framework, this refers to the achievement of a fulfilled human life, a notion which may vary strongly across different societies and groups within

societies. It is a context-dependent state of individuals and human groups, comprising aspects such as access to food, water, energy and livelihood security and also health, good social relationships and equity, security, cultural identity and freedom of choice and action. “Human wellbeing”, “inclusive wealth”, “living in harmony with nature”, “living-well in balance and harmony with Mother Earth” are examples of different perspectives on a “good quality of life” (IPBES, 2019a, 2021).

Governance: The way the rules, norms and actions in a given organization are structured, sustained and regulated (IPBES, 2019a).

Green technology: An emerging idea with the primary objective of promoting sustainable development, which entails identifying environment-friendly sources of growth, promoting new environment-friendly industries and creating jobs and technologies by lowering environmental risks and ecological scarcities, pollution and carbon emissions, improving energy and resource efficiency and preventing the loss of biodiversity (Kaliappan *et al.*, 2023).

Greenwashing: The act of making false or misleading statements about the environmental benefits of a product or practice (*What Is Greenwashing?*, 2023). The European Supervisory Authorities (EBA, EIOPA and ESMA – ESAs) define greenwashing as a practice where sustainability-related statements, declarations, actions, or communications do not clearly and fairly reflect the underlying sustainability profile of an entity, a financial product, or financial services. This practice may be misleading to consumers, investors, or other market participants (ESMA, 2024).

Growth paradigm: A term first introduced by ecological economist Herman Daly (Daly, 1972) to characterize the preanalytic vision of mainstream economists that justified their belief in unlimited growth (Vanasupa & Schlemer, 2016).

H

Health: A state of complete physical, social and mental well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity (World Health Organization, 2021). In this assessment, health includes the role of ecological, environmental, socio-economic, cultural and health system factors.

Heuristics: Often characterized as rules of thumb that can be used to speed up the process of decision-making (Hjeij & Vilks, 2023).

Human rights: The inalienable fundamental rights of each human being as acknowledged in the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights (United Nations, 1948).

Human well-being: A perspective on a good life that comprises access to basic resources, freedom and choice, health and physical, including psychological, well-being, good social relationships, security, equity, peace of mind and spiritual experience. Well-being is achieved when individuals and communities can act meaningfully to pursue their goals and can enjoy a good quality of life. The concept of human well-being is used in many western societies and its variants, together with living in harmony with nature and living well in balance and harmony with Mother Earth. All these are different perspectives on a good quality of life (IPBES, 2019a).

Hurai: “All the best things” expresses the logic of transforming from nature to animals and then to human beings, in accord with Chinese Tuvan’s people’s cosmology. It sustains the belief that human beings are capable of continuously receiving the Hurai and blessing from nature (Hou, 2019). Origin: Tuva, Siberia (China, Mongolia, Russia).

Inclusive governance: Governance approaches that recognize multiple actors, values and knowledge systems engaged through co-production of solutions.

Inclusive innovation: Harnesses science, technology and innovation “know-how” to address the needs of lower income groups (OECD, 2013). This definition has later been expanded beyond lower income groups (Levidow & Papaioannou, 2018).

Incremental change: In this assessment, it refers to a small shift in the nature and directionality of a process that contributes to transformative change for a just and sustainable world. This recognizes that transformative change takes place over time through a number of small shifts occurring across sectors and scales. Seemingly small changes can spread in ways that inspire

or influence larger and more systemic shifts, especially when they address the underlying causes and overcome barriers and challenges to transformative change (see **Chapter 1**).

Indigenous and local knowledge: The knowledge, practices and innovations embedded in the relationships of Indigenous Peoples and local communities to nature (IPBES, 2019a).

Indigenous Peoples and local communities: As used in the IPBES Global Assessment, Indigenous Peoples and local communities is a term used internationally by representatives, organizations and conventions to refer to individuals and communities who are, on the one hand, self-identified as Indigenous and [or], on the other hand, are members of local communities that maintain inter-generational connection to place and nature through livelihood, cultural identity and worldviews, institutions and ecological knowledge. The term is not intended to ignore differences and diversity within and among Indigenous Peoples and between them and local communities; Indigenous Peoples have recognized and distinct rights, which are not extendable to the broader and encompassing concept of local communities (IPBES, 2019a).

Individualism: The moral stance, political philosophy, ideology and social outlook that emphasizes the intrinsic worth of the individual (Wood, 1972).

Inequality: Uneven opportunities and social positions and processes of discrimination within a group or society, based on gender, class, ethnicity, age and (dis)ability, often produced by uneven development (IPCC, 2022). Social inequality refers to a state whereby resources in a given society are distributed unevenly, typically through norms of allocation, that engender specific patterns along lines of socially defined categories of persons (IPBES, 2021).

Inner dimensions of sustainability: Subjective aspects of sustainability, such as individual and collective values, beliefs, worldviews, paradigms and consciousness. Sometimes referred to as the personal sphere of transformation, related inner capacities and skills influence how people perceive and engage with structures and practices for transformative change (O’Brien, 2018; Wamsler *et al.*, 2021).

Inner transformation (for sustainability):

The unleashing of people's inner potential and capacity to commit to and effect change for a more sustainable life across individual, collective, organisational and system levels (Sharma, 2007; Wamsler & Osberg, 2022).

Innovation: An idea, practice, or object perceived as new by an individual or other unit of adoption (Rogers, 2003). Initial definitions of innovation refer to "commercialized invention" essential for long term economic growth and labour productivity (Schot & Steinmueller, 2018).

Innovation system: A concept involving agents, networks and institutions working towards the overall function of developing, disseminating and using new products and processes (Hayashi, 2020).

Institutions: Institutions are the humanly devised arrangements that structure political, economic and social interaction, consisting of both informal (e.g., taboos, customs, traditions and codes of conduct) and formal rules (e.g., constitutions, laws, property rights) (North, 1991).

Institutional misfits: Several types of situations (social, spatial, temporal and functional) that reflect incompatibility or incongruence between the properties of formal and/or informal institutional arrangements with those of the socio-ecological systems they are embedded in and that may lead to a series of sustainability challenges (O. Young, 2008).

Instrumental value: The value attributed to something not as an end in itself but as a means of achieving a particular end (IPBES, 2021).

Integrated approach: A holistic, transdisciplinary approach to sustainability research, policy and practice that recognizes relationships and interactions across different perspectives, including interior and exterior and individual and collective domains (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2020).

Interconnectedness: A term used to describe the interdependence of humans with nature, it has been emphasized in eastern religions such as Buddhism that claim that the boundaries between self and others, as well as self and environment, are blurred or even non-existent, though some variations of these ideas also have a history

in the west and have been employed by western psychologists (Davis *et al.*, 2009). Relational approaches to transformative change take into account dynamic and holistic accounts of human-nature interconnectedness (West *et al.*, 2020).

Intrinsic value: The ethical or philosophical value that an object has, in and of itself. It is the actual value of an asset based on underlying perceptions of both tangible and intangible factors (IPBES, 2022b).

J

Just: Describes what is considered moral or ethical. It is often conflated with equity and fairness. All notions and interpretations of just and justice are normative constructs and have merits and drawbacks relative to each other (Ikeme, 2003).

Justice: Traditionally refers to the fair treatment of people, or 'what we owe to each other', but its scope may also be extended to include duties to other units of nature such as animals, rivers or Pachamama (IPBES, 2021). Justice also refers to a variegated set of conditions – primarily concerned with distribution of resources, political processes and social recognition – that allows for full human flourishing. In this assessment, the concept of justice relates to procedural justice, distributional justice, recognition justice, restorative justice and multispecies justice (Agyeman *et al.*, 2016; Celermajor *et al.*, 2020).

K

Kametsa asaike: Living well together in this place; knowing the world as a network of mutually constituted human and other-than-human actors (Caruso & Sarmiento Barletti, 2019). Origin: Ashaninka, Peruvian Amazon.

Kawsak Sacha: The living forest, a conscious living being who is the subject of rights and is inhabited by Runayuk, beings that protect ecosystems, animal and plant species (IPBES, 2022b). Origin: Kichwa, Ecuador.

Kciye: A Penawahpskek word translated as meaning harmony with the natural world entailing both recognition of interconnectedness and adopting attitudes, beliefs and actions that enact this in practice (Mitchell, 2018). Origin: Wabanaki, North America.

Knowledge system: A body of propositions that are adhered to, whether formally or informally and are routinely used to claim truth. They are organized structures and dynamic processes a) generating and representing content, components, classes, or types of knowledge, that are b) domain-specific or characterized by domain-relevant features as defined by the user or consumer, c) reinforced by a set of logical relationships that connect the content of knowledge to its value (utility), d) enhanced by a set of iterative processes that enable the evolution, revision, adaptation and advances and e) subject to criteria of relevance, reliability and quality (IPBES, 2021).

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity

Framework: A multilateral environmental framework adopted during the fifteenth meeting of the Conference of the Parties (COP 15) to the Convention on Biological Diversity following a four-year consultation and negotiation process. It supports the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals and builds on the Convention's previous Strategic Plans and sets out an ambitious pathway to reach the global vision of a world living in harmony with nature by 2050. Among the Framework's key elements are four goals for 2050 and 23 targets for 2030 (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022).

L

Land degradation: Refers to the many processes that drive the decline or loss in biodiversity, ecosystem functions or their benefits to people and includes the degradation of all terrestrial ecosystems (IPBES, 2018a).

Lekil kuxlejaj: In the Mayan language tseltal, the most similar word *islekil kuxlejaj* (Paoli, 2003), which means 'good life', that is, what is done in order to integrate material, spiritual and communal needs (Ávila, 2011). Origin: Maya, Chiapas, Mexico.

Leverage points: Places in a system where relatively minor interventions can lead to relatively major changes in certain outcomes (Fischer & Riechers, 2019; Meadows, 1999).

Living in harmony with nature: Within the context of the IPBES Conceptual Framework - a perspective on good quality of life based on the interdependence that exists among human beings, other living species and elements of nature. It implies

that we should live peacefully alongside all other organisms even though we may need to exploit other organisms to some degree (IPBES, 2021).

Lock-in traps: A situation in which the future development of a system, including infrastructure, technologies, investments, institutions and behavioural norms, is determined or constrained ('locked in') by historical developments (IPCC, n.d.).

M

Marginalisation: Refers to the set of processes through which some individuals and groups face systematic disadvantages in their interactions with dominant social, political and economic institutions. The disadvantages arise from class status, social group identity (kinship, ethnicity, caste and race categories), political affiliation, gender, age and disability (IPBES, 2019a).

Materialism: The belief that consumer goods and services provide the greatest source of satisfaction and value (Belk, 1985).

Mental models: A concentrated, personally constructed, internal conception of external phenomena (historical, existing or projected), or experience that affects how a person acts (Rook, 2013).

Metabolic rift: The disruption or imbalance in relationship between human societies and nature, often in the context of industrial capitalism (Foster, 1999).

Mindset: The basic assumptions, beliefs, core values, goals and expectations shared by a group of people and what they use as rules to guide their attitudes and practices (Fang *et al.*, 2004).

Mino-mnaamodzawin: The value of 'respect for the spirit in all things is rooted in Indigenous legal orders' (IPBES, 2022b). Origin: Anishinaabek, United States of America.

Mino-bimaatisiwin: Translated as living a good life/balanced life, it refers to a basic principle that informs a larger set of principles and protocols in human actions that are manifested not only in offerings, reverence, non-greed and non-waste, but are used to make decisions affecting community landscapes. *Mino-bimaatisiwin* is embedded within a holistic world view

and thus involves living in respectful and reciprocal terms with all of creation at individual and collective levels. It recognizes that reciprocal relations are required not only among people, but with all other 'relatives' as well: animals; plants; rocks; water; spirits; celestial beings such as the moon, sun and stars; ancestors; and those yet to come (IPBES, 2022b). Origin: Anishinaabek, United States of America.

Modernity: Notions shaped by coloniality that idealize and promote control-oriented, mechanistic and reductionist ways of reasoning, generating knowledge, organizing structures and political representation and underpin industrial production (Stirling, 2019).

Monitoring, evaluation and learning

(MEL): Monitoring is a systematic process for collecting and reviewing data and information across the life of a project (rather than just at the end). It was designed to track, monitor and evaluate outcomes in a participatory manner that enables learning and capacity development of project participants. MEL systems provide tools and methodologies to: i) assess changes in functional capacities and their effects on agricultural innovation systems, ii) support the adaptation and refinement of capacity strengthening to achieve greater impacts and iii) stimulate continuous learning by using participatory monitoring and evaluation approaches (see **Chapter 5**).

Mother Earth: An expression used in a number of countries and regions to refer to the planet Earth and the entity that sustains all living things found in nature with which humans have an indivisible, interdependent physical and spiritual relationship (IPBES, 2021).

N

Nanao ñu'u: To rediscover human-nature bonds and reconnect with values of equity, respect and care with *nanao ñu'u* (our mother), in the Tu'un Javi language, which recognizes seven types/names for rain (IPBES, 2022b). Origin: Mixtec, Mexico.

Narrative: Qualitative descriptions of plausible future world evolutions, describing the characteristics, general logic and developments underlying a particular quantitative set of scenarios. Narratives are also referred to in the literature as "storylines" (IPCC, n.d.).

Natural resources: Refers to metals, minerals, fossil fuels, biomass, water and land. These resources can be tracked as flows through the economy: from extraction, through processing and consumption, to point of reuse or discarding at end-of-life (UNEP, 2017).

Natural social contracts: The collective power of societies, people and nature for dealing with the polycrisis of the 21st century (including inequalities, injustices, distrust, climate and ecological crises) through implicit or explicit collective agreements (at multiple governance levels) among members of a society to cooperate with one another and abide by certain rules or norms targeted at sustainability, equity and justice, while departing from a different worldview (eco-centric or Earth-centric instead of anthropocentric), a different view of humanity (*homo ecologicus/florens* instead of *homo economicus*) and different economies and cultures -regenerative instead of linear- (Huntjens *et al.*, 2023).

Nature: In the context of IPBES, nature refers to the natural world with an emphasis on its living components. Within the context of western science, it includes categories such as biodiversity, ecosystems (both structure and functioning), evolution, the biosphere; humankind's shared evolutionary heritage and biocultural diversity. Within the context of other knowledge systems, it includes categories such as Mother Earth and systems of life and it is often viewed as inextricably linked to humans, not as a separate entity (IPBES, 2021, 2022a).

Nature deficit disorder: Idea that an urbanized lifestyle, including fewer natural spaces, a car-focused culture, more screen time, changes in the perception of risk, less leisure time and increased time pressures from work or school, combine to decrease or even eliminate contact with nature for both adults and children (Warber *et al.*, 2015).

Nature's contributions to people: All contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature (i.e., all organisms, ecosystems and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to people's quality of life (IPBES, 2019a).

Nature-based solutions: Actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems

which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services, resilience and biodiversity benefits (UNEP, 2022).

Neoliberalism: A set of governmental policies and practices that took hold in the 1980s wherein States de-regulated to facilitate increased flows of capital throughout the globe (Bloom, 2017).

Nexus: The interlinkages between biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change, including their social, economic and environmental components and how the elements interact across scales, geographic regions and ecosystems (in agreement with the IPBES Nexus Assessment (IPBES, 2024)).

Non-human entities: Elements of the natural world that are not human but are recognized as having intrinsic value, agency, or rights. These entities include animals, plants, ecosystems and other elements of nature. The concept challenges the anthropocentric view that places humans at the centre of moral consideration and instead promotes a more inclusive perspective that acknowledges the intrinsic worth of non-human elements of the environment (Alves *et al.*, 2023; Delorme *et al.*, 2024).

Normative principles: Sentences or statements that makes claims regarding what ought to be done, categorically or hypothetically (Henderson, 2002).

O

Ontology: Implicit or explicit understandings about what is, including the kinds and structures of objects, properties, events, processes and relations in every area of reality (Smith, 1999). The philosophical study of the nature of being, becoming, existence, or reality, as well as the basic categories of being and their relations (IPBES, 2019a).

P

Paradigms: Dominant thought patterns based on a deep set of beliefs and shared social agreements about the nature of reality and how the world works (Meadows, 1999).

Pathways: In this assessment, pathways refer to descriptions of different strategies for moving from the current situation

towards a desired future vision or set of specified targets. They are descriptions of purposive courses of actions that build on each other, from short-term to long-term actions into broader transformation. They are closely related to normative or policy or target-seeking scenarios (IPBES, 2021).

Path dependency: Technologies and economic systems heavily determined by historical events, or the timing and sequence of political junctures that shape institutional decisions which are then too costly to reverse (Goldstein *et al.*, 2023).

Patriarchy: A system of relationships, beliefs and values embedded in political, social and economic systems that structure gender inequality between men and women (Nash, 2009).

Planetary health: Describes the health of human civilisations and the natural systems on which they depend; a new interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach that aims to investigate the effects of environmental change on human health and to study the political, economic and social systems that govern those effects (The Lancet Planetary Health, 2017).

Planned obsolescence: A business strategy to ensure that a technology or product becomes outdated and/or unusable after a predetermined period (Kramer, 2012).

Pluralism: The existence or inclusion of a diverse range of views, paradigms, knowledge systems and practices, perspectives, interpretations, or disciplines. Pluralist processes are based on a commitment to be inclusive of this plurality in ways that recognize and respect difference and that remain open to ongoing contestation, renegotiation and change (Pascual *et al.*, 2021).

Plurality: The existence or inclusion of a diverse range of perspectives, practices, interpretations, or disciplines. It suggests that there are multiple viewpoints, approaches and understandings within a given context. It recognizes that different languages, research traditions and cultural contexts may contribute to a rich and varied understanding of the subject matter, while also acknowledging the potential challenges of navigating and translating these diverse perspectives. It is used to highlight the importance of incorporating a variety of perspectives and disciplines in order to

recognize and honour this diversity through the development of context specific forms of engagement, that include diverse actors, visions and worldviews and remain open to ongoing contestation, renegotiation and change. Plurality therefore includes within it a commitment to ongoing renegotiation of power (Pascual *et al.*, 2021).

Pluriverse: A multiplicity of possible worlds, often in contrast to the concept modernist ontology of universalism (Kothari *et al.*, 2019).

Policy: A definite course or method of action selected from among alternatives and in light of given conditions to guide and determine present and future decisions (IPBES, 2021).

Policy autonomy: Delegation of authority to agencies to become actively engaged in policy formulation (Bach, 2012).

Policy inertia: Lack of evidence-based policy formulation and policy coherence through learning and feedback mechanisms (IPBES, 2019a).

Policy instrument: Policy instruments are understood as the different interventions (formal rules, laws, social norms and processes etc.) made by decision makers (governments and public authorities, intergovernmental organizations, companies etc.) to ensure that (public) policy objectives are supported and achieved by influencing the behaviour of other stakeholders. The IPBES Catalogue differentiates among four different types of policy instruments: i) economic and financial instruments (financial incentives handling out or taking away economic resources), ii) legal and regulatory instruments (formal rules, laws and regulations), iii) rights-based instruments and customary norms (incl. human and collective rights as well as customary norms and institutions of indigenous people) and iv) social and cultural instruments -information-based instruments and voluntary or collective actions with an emphasis on the intertwined relationships between ecosystems and sociocultural dynamics (IPBES, 2022b).

Policy option: Defined in terms of their ability to achieve the stated policy goals (IPBES, 2021). In this assessment, potential course of action or decision that can be taken by a government, organization, or individual to address a particular issue or

achieve a specific goal. In the context of government and public administration, policy options are the different choices available to policymakers when designing and implementing policies. These options are often based on analysis, research and consideration of various factors, including social, economic and political implications. Policy options can range from regulatory measures and legislative changes to financial incentives, awareness campaigns and international cooperation. The selection of a policy option depends on the goals and values of the decision makers, as well as the context and nature of the issue at hand (**Chapter 5**).

Polycrisis: A situation where two or more crises, which may or may not be independent, become causally entangled, such that the interactive effects among them escalate the severity of impacts of each and thereby significantly degrade global planetary health and humanity's prospects for wellbeing in a relatively short period of time (UNEP, 2024).

Population dynamics: Population dynamics is the study of why population numbers change in time and space and how these processes operate through biological, social and environmental processes (Turchin, 2003). Population dynamics include population size, age structure, urbanization and migration.

Power: The capacity of actors to mobilize agency, resources and discourses, as well as to utilize or shape institutions to achieve a goal. Power can be both constraining and enabling and the capacity of one actor can inhibit the capacity of another actor. Power in the context of human-nature relationships can be manifested in multiple and non-exclusive ways through discourses and social structures. Discursive power is the power to use discourses or knowledge production to shape worldviews, identities and values. Related to this is the power to frame how issues are understood, communicated and discussed (framing power). Structural power is the result of historically-specific socio-cultural, political and economic systems that reproduce social positions and/or hierarchies among social groups. Structural power relations determine, for example, who has the power to make rules regarding access, use and responsibilities about nature/nature's contributions to people and who is excluded from this process (rule-making power); as well who has the formal or informal rights regarding nature/

nature's contributions to people, which in turn determines the use of these assets and whose values are emphasized (operational power) (IPBES, 2021).

Power relations: A system of established or emergent connections among elements and members of a social system. Influence, resources and knowledge flow along and through power relations to shape views, structures and practices from the micro to the macro levels. In this sense, power is not something that a particular person or collective possesses permanently or immutably, but a quality that becomes evident and can be appreciated in the way it flows through relationships among them to influence personal and social outcomes (Avelino & Wittmayer, 2016; Berbés-Blázquez *et al.*, 2016).

Powerful actors: Refers to individuals, groups, institutions or organisations that have the capacity or potential to make or receive any change, or to resist it. Actors may derive power from their action or inaction, as well as through their properties - e.g., charisma or attractive cultures or ideologies (Lukes, 2005).

Practices: Tangible, mental, or social activities routinely operated by humans to interact in social-ecological systems (Dubuisson-Quellier & Plessz, 2013). In this assessment, practices refer to ways of doing, behaving, or relating. Practices can include individual behaviours and consumption practices, the use of technologies and the decisions we take (including policy and management-related decision-making).

Principles: A framework for understanding, reasoning and making judgments. They often represent values or beliefs that guide decisions and behaviours (Rachels & Rachels, 2015).

Protected area: A clearly defined geographical space, recognized, dedicated and managed, through legal or other effective means, to achieve the long-term conservation of nature with associated ecosystem services and cultural values (IPBES, 2021).

R

Racism: A global hierarchy of superiority and inferiority along the line of the human that has been politically, culturally and economically produced and reproduced

for centuries by dominant institutions.

The people classified as above the line of the human are recognized socially in their humanity as human beings and, thus, enjoy access to rights (human rights, civil rights, women rights and/or labour rights), material resources and social recognition to their subjectivities, identities, epistemologies and spiritualities. The people below the line of the human are considered subhuman or non-human; and the extension of rights, material resources and the recognition of their subjectivities, identities, spiritualities and epistemologies are denied (Grosfoguel, 2016).

Rebound effects: Counter-intuitive causal mechanisms whereby improvements in energy efficiency result not in lower but higher consumption rates (Font Vivanco *et al.*, 2016).

Reciprocity: In this assessment, reciprocity refers to giving back to the Earth in equal measure for what is taken. This definition is rooted in an understanding that the Earth is populated by non-human beings deserving of respect and that balance in ecological systems arises from cycles of giving and taking. Reciprocity among different parts of the living Earth produces equilibrium, in which all life can flourish. This reciprocity includes healing damages that have been done and being partners in renewal (Kimmerer, 2014).

Reflexivity: That which takes account of itself or a person's self. Mental operations that are turned or directed back on the mind itself (Holland, 1999; Salzman, 2002).

Reformist responses (in the context of biodiversity): Interventions that work through existing systems to modify current structures and practices, such as corporate behaviour, to ameliorate impacts on biodiversity while leaving underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline intact (Acosta, 2013; Santika *et al.*, 2024).

Regeneration: Dynamic processes of renewal or re-creation of desired outcomes, often after disturbances. Regeneration involves deepening relational values and responsibilities that nourish human-nature relationships by reviving local culture and nature. It is considered distinct from restoration, unless the system resulting from restoration is, at least to an extent, dynamically self-perpetuating (Fischer *et al.*, 2024; Gordon *et al.*, 2023).

Regenerative agriculture: An approach to farming and land management that focuses on restoring and improving the health of ecosystems. The goal is not only to sustainably produce food but also to regenerate the soil, water and biodiversity, ultimately creating a more resilient and sustainable agricultural system (Tiftonnell *et al.*, 2022).

Relational values: The importance of desirable, meaningful and often reciprocal relationships - beyond means to an end - between humans and nature and among humans (including across generations) through nature - e.g., sense of place, spirituality, responsibility, care, reciprocity, stewardship (IPBES, 2021).

Relations of domination: In this assessment, a way of relating that is considered both an underlying cause and a barrier to transformative change. It consists of seven dimensions: i) categorizing nature and people as different elements with different rights and power; ii) stratifying and separating different groups in a way that promotes subordination; iii) reducing people and ecologies to singular, often standardized dimensions that lend themselves to management; iv) quantifying and aggregating values in a manner that promotes v) technocratic approaches to conservation and other relationships with biodiversity which in turn can be used to vi) justify the appropriation and extraction of resources in a manner that vii) concentrates and accumulates these on behalf of the most privileged interests (**Chapter 4**).

Response options: The diverse range of human actions to address specific issues, needs, objectives, opportunities, or problems in the governance and management of the nexus that account for a diversity of worldviews, behaviours, norms and values. Response options can encompass combinations of voluntary or mandatory policies, strategies, measures and interventions that are intended, designed and/or implemented to change nexus elements and interlinkages between nexus elements directly and those that modify direct or indirect drivers shaping the nexus. The response options presented in this assessment are a non-exhaustive list, with implementation dependent on national and local circumstances (**Chapters 1 and 4**).

Restoration: Any intentional activity that initiates or accelerates the recovery of an

ecosystem from a degraded state. Active restoration includes a range of human interventions aimed at influencing and accelerating natural successional processes to recover biodiversity ecosystem service provision. Passive restoration includes reliance primarily on natural process of ecological succession to restore degraded ecosystems, but may include measures to protect a site from processes that currently prevent natural recovery (e.g., protection of degraded forests from overgrazing by livestock or unintentional human-induced fire) (IPBES, 2019a).

S

Sacred natural sites: Areas of land or water that have special spiritual significance to peoples and communities. They consist of natural features, ranging from entire ecosystems, such as mountains, forests or islands, to single natural features such as a tree, spring or boulder and are very important for the conservation of nature and culture. Sacred natural sites have been managed based on Indigenous and local knowledge systems, developed over long periods of time and are source of cultural identity (IPBES, 2021).

Saffu: This principle guides people's lives and impels them to respect and do justice to one's own *ayyaana* (spirit) and that of other beings (IPBES, 2022b). Origin: Oromo, Ethiopia.

Satoyama, Satoumi, Fūdo: The entwined relations between people-and-nature and people-and-people expressed through living in nature exist in myriad ways, e.g., in the Japanese concepts, reflecting dynamic relationships between people, habitats and species (IPBES, 2022b). Origin: Japan.

Scale: The spatial, temporal, quantitative and analytical dimensions used to measure and study any phenomenon. The temporal scale is comprised of two properties:

i) temporal extent - the total length of the time period of interest for a particular study (e.g., 10 years, 50 years, or 100 years); and ii) temporal grain (or resolution) - the temporal frequency with which data are observed or projected within this total period (e.g., at 1-year, 5-year or 10- year intervals). The spatial scale is comprised of two properties: i) spatial extent - the size of the total area of interest for a particular study (e.g., a watershed, a country, the entire planet); and ii) spatial grain (or

resolution) - the size of the spatial units within this total area for which data are observed or predicted, e.g., fine-grained or coarse-grained grid cells (IPBES, 2021).

Scaling: Accelerating the adoption and implementation of socio-political and response options, amplifying their impacts and normalizing them as mainstream solutions to nexus challenges. Scaling is often referred to through processes of scaling up (e.g., institutionalizing socio-political and response options at the level of policy, rules and laws), scaling out (e.g., replicating and/or spreading/transferring socio-political and response options to new places and/or geographies with similar contexts) and scaling deep, e.g., transforming people's hearts and minds, their values and cultural practices and the quality of relationships (Moore *et al.*, 2015).

Scenarios: Plausible stories about how the future may unfold that can be told in words, numbers, illustrations and/or maps—often combining quantitative and qualitative elements (IPBES, 2019a). They are not predictions about the future; rather possibilities used in situations of large uncertainty, based on specified, internally consistent sets of underlying assumptions (IPBES, 2016; Raskin, 2005), based on a coherent and internally consistent set of assumptions about key driving forces and relationships (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005).

Shareholder primacy: A prevailing theory in corporate governance, which holds that shareholder interests should be prioritized relative to all other corporate stakeholders (Kersten & Shivakumar, 2022).

Siida: Consisting of the people, land and the reindeer herd, together create a unit that has deep knowledge of the landscape and on how to adapt to available resources (Sara, 2001). Origin: Sàmi communities.

Social justice: Specific habit of justice that is “social” in that it inspires, works with and organizes others to accomplish together a work of justice and that it aims at the good of the community (all) rather than that of one agent (Novak, 2000).

Social movements: Social processes where actors i) share a distinct collective identity, ii) connect through dense informal networks and iii) engage in conflictual collective action (Della Porta & Diani, 2020).

Socialism: A political, philosophical and economic system in which the means of production are collectively controlled, rather than owned by private corporations as they are under capitalism, or by aristocrats under feudalism (Sherwin, 2020).

Socio-ecological systems (also social-ecological systems): Complex adaptive systems in which people and nature are inextricably linked, in which both the social and ecological components exert strong influence over outcomes (IPBES, 2022c).

Socioeconomic transformations: Co-evolutionary processes that include changes in modes of production, work relations and culture (Kemp *et al.*, 2018).

Socionature: A concept that conveys that society and nature are inseparable and should not be analysed in abstraction from each other. They are always co-productive (Bear, 2017).

Sociotechnical infrastructures: The emergent systems that organize people and technologies such as databases, information systems, maps, metrics, instruments and more to enable a wide range of actors to know and act in specific ways regarding all kinds of contemporary matters including biodiversity loss (Blok *et al.*, 2016).

Sociotechnical transitions: Long-term complex systemic change processes involving multiple actors. Associated with deep structural changes in transport, energy, agri-food and other systems, involving alterations in their overall configuration - includes technology, policy, markets, consumer practices, infrastructure, cultural meaning and scientific knowledge (Geels, 2011).

Spheres of influence: In this assessment, it refers to the domain in which a person (or organisation) has the capacity to encourage or effect meaningful change. This includes the range of people and topics they have the potential to engage with and the spatial reach of their actions, ideas or decisions, as well as the specific context, stakeholders, or systems that can be shaped by their identity and interests (**Chapter 1**).

Spirituality: The search for the sacred in oneself. Religion is the institutionalisation of such search - which can be compatible or incompatible with spirituality depending on the context (de Kalbermatten, 2003; Hill *et al.*, 2000).

Spiritual reconnection: Refers to personal and collective practices, processes and outcomes regarding the actualization of the potential to connect to and experience the sacred or the reflection of the divine within oneself. This has been referred to as the spirit, the self, the kingdom of God, resurrection and other terms by different spiritual or religious traditions around the world (de Kalbermatten, 2003).

Stakeholder: Any individual, group or organization that is interested in, engages, affects or could be affected (whether positively or negatively) by a particular issue and its associated policies, decisions and action. Adapted from the IPBES Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species (2022c).

Structures: The stable norms, rules, regulations, institutions and governance arrangements that influence how societies and individuals function. Structures generate consistent patterns in social behaviours, interactions and relationships. In dynamic analyses, they both affect and are emergent from patterns of behaviours and interactions. In this assessment, they broadly refer to ways of organising, regulating and governing (Porpora, 1989; Stinchcombe, 2015).

Suma qamaña: A term from the Aymara people meaning living well together with harmonious relationships between people and nature (Albó, 2018; Artaraz & Calestani, 2015). Origin: Bolivia.

Sumak Kawsay and Suma Qamaña: Indigenous Andean worldviews in South America that conceptualizes a good quality of life through broad values that guide human-human and human-nature interconnections (Artaraz & Calestani, 2015; IPBES, 2022b). Living well implies a strong ethical component of valuing and appreciating the distinctiveness of others, as well as spirituality or lifestyle and so can never be just economic (Albó, 2018). Origin: Kichwa & Aymara, South America, Bolivia.

Sustainability: See Sustainable development.

Sustainable development: Defined by the World Commission for Environment and Development (1987) as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Acknowledging its normative, social

and political nature, a process-oriented definition considers sustainability to be the emergent property of a conversation about desired futures that is informed by some understandings of the ecological, social and economic consequences of different courses of action (Robinson, 2004).

Sustainable Development Goals: A set of goals adopted by the United Nations on September 25, 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure prosperity for all. Each goal has specific targets to be achieved over the next 15 years (IPBES, 2021; United Nations, 2015).

Sustainable resource management: Refers to both ensuring that consumption does not exceed levels of sustainable supply and, ensuring that the earth's systems are able to perform their natural functions (i.e., preventing disruptions, as in the case of greenhouse gas emissions affecting the ability of the atmosphere to 'regulate' the earth's temperature). It requires monitoring and management at various scales. The aim of sustainable resource management is to ensure the long-term material basis of societies in a way that neither resource extraction and use nor the deposition of waste and emissions will surpass the thresholds of a safe operating space (UNEP, 2017).

System: A group of interacting or interrelated elements that act according to a set of rules to form a unified whole. A system, surrounded and influenced by its environment, is described by its boundaries, structure and purpose and expressed in its functioning. Also refers to a set of elements or parts that is coherently organized and interconnected in a pattern or structure that produces a characteristic set of behaviours, often classified as its function or purpose (Meadows, 2008). In the transformative change assessment, systems and their boundaries are recognized as subjective rather than realist objects.

Synergies: Positive interactions that produce a combined effect greater than the sum of their separate effects (IPBES, 2016).

Systems thinking: A way of thinking about the web of interrelations linked to complex problems, our relationship with the world and how change happens (Voulvoulis *et al.*, 2022). Systems thinking moves the focus from entities to relationships among them. There

are ontological (systems viewed as real-world phenomena) and epistemological (systems as a lens through which sustainability issues can be addressed) approaches to systems thinking (Abson *et al.*, 2017).

T

Technocracy: A form of governance that is strongly reliant on elite technical experts, whose understandings are distinctively based on forms of scientific and technical knowledge that emphasize categorization, simplification and measurement of nature and the classification and stratification of people or societies (Arias-Maldonado & Trachtenberg, 2019; Stirling, 2023).

Technology: The application of scientific and other knowledge to practical tasks by ordered systems that involve people and organizations, production actions and skill, living organisms and machines (Robson & Tsou, 2023).

Technology transfer: The process of applying extant technology to new and innovative applications (Lane, 1999).

Telecoupling: Refers to socioeconomic and environmental interactions over distances. It involves distant exchanges of information, energy and matter (e.g., people, goods, products, capital) at multiple spatial, temporal and organizational scales (IPBES, 2019a).

Territories of life: Refers to the unique areas which are under the governance, management and conservation of Indigenous peoples and local communities. Such territories are defined by a connection to the land which transcends the physical and serves as a source of cultural and social identity and a link connecting past generations to present inhabitants. Further, territories of life exist wherever pertinent decisions are made via a functioning governance institution composed by the custodian peoples or local communities. Overall, such territories positively contribute to both the conservation of nature as well as the livelihood and wellbeing of the local communities (CCA Consortium, 2021).

Tipping point: A set of conditions of an ecological or social system where further perturbation will cause rapid change and prevent the system from returning to its former state (IPBES, 2021). Biophysical tipping points refer to these conditions when they occur in ecological, climate and other

interacting biological and physical processes and they can occur gradually or abruptly (Pörtner *et al.*, 2021). Social tipping points refer to situations where small changes trigger a non-linear change in the social component of the system, driven by self-reinforcing positive feedback mechanisms that often irreversibly lead to a qualitatively different state of the social system (Milkoreit *et al.*, 2018).

Tiwizi (ⵜⵉⵣⵉⵣⵉⵙⵜ): Amazigh word for group work or mutual aid. Tiwizi is done within the tribe, to work together to benefit everyone, for example building an agadir (ⴰⵖⴰⵎⴰⵔ), (fortified communal granary) igoudar (ⵉⵖⵓⵔⴰⵔ) (traditional granary) or taddagh (ⵜⴰⵔⴰⵔⴰⵖ) (road) (IPBES, 2023). Origin: North Africa.

Transdisciplinary: An approach to research that is based on integration of multiple disciplines and the active inclusion and participation of stakeholders representing different societal sectors in the processes of problem formulation, knowledge production and learning (Angelstam *et al.*, 2013). It often focuses on specific, complex and societally relevant real-world situations or problems and emphasizes working in a transformative manner to proactively support action or intervention, with an orientation toward the common good and betterment of society (Lawrence *et al.*, 2022).

Transformation: A change in the fundamental attributes of natural and human systems, or a thorough or dramatic change in form, composition, structure, appearance, or functionality. In terms of systems, it refers to changes that are fundamental, broad and deep (IPCC, 2022); Transformations can lead to both desirable and undesirable outcomes (Blythe *et al.*, 2018).

Transformative capacities: The knowledge, skills, attitudes and resources necessary to realize transformative change (Chapter 1). These include the capacities of individuals and organisations to transform themselves and their society in deliberate, conscious ways to imagine, enact and sustain a transformed world and a way of life that is in balance and where all life flourishes (Ziervogel *et al.*, 2016).

Transformative change: A fundamental, system-wide reorganization across technological, economic and social factors, including paradigms, goals and

values (IPBES, 2019a). In this assessment, transformative change for a just and sustainable world is defined as fundamental, system-wide shifts in views, structures and practices that address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. Deliberate transformative change for a just and sustainable world is guided by four principles: i) equity and justice; ii) pluralism and inclusion; iii) respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships; and iv) adaptive learning and action.

Transformative governance: The formal and informal (public and private) rules, rule-making systems and actor-networks at all levels of human society (from local to global) that enable transformative change for a just and sustainable world (Visseren-Hamakers *et al.*, 2021; Visseren-Hamakers & Kok, 2022). In this assessment, transformative governance involves shifting views, structures and practices to overcome lock-ins through integrative governance that revises decision-making processes; inclusive governance that creates ownership and deliberation among stakeholders; global and multi-level governance that addresses global interdependencies and global commons issues; and adaptive governance that continuously evaluates and revises regulatory and holds responsible actors accountable for addressing biodiversity related issues (Chapter 5).

Transformative innovation policy: Focuses on innovation as a search process on the system level, guided by social and environmental objectives, informed by experience and the learning that accompanies that experience and a willingness to revisit existing arrangements to de-routinize them to address societal challenges (Schot & Steinmueller, 2018).

Transformative learning: The process of transforming problematic frames of reference associated with assumptions and expectations (mindsets, habits of mind, meaning perspectives) to make them more inclusive, discriminating, open, reflective and emotionally able to change (Mezirow, 1997).

Transformative potential: A latent quality, characteristic or capacity for realising fundamental, system-wide shifts in views, structures and practices to address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. Transformative potential can be realized through the development of transformative capacities, which include the

knowledge, skills, attitudes and resources necessary to realize transformative change (**Chapter 1**).

Transition: The process of changing from one state or condition to another in a given period of time. Transitions can involve individuals, firms, cities, regions and nations and can be based on incremental or transformative change (IPCC, 2022). See Socio-technical transitions.

U

Ubuntu: The relational values system of the Ubuntu philosophy focuses on reciprocity, dialogue and collective humanity, which are extended to nature and have been applied in development, external relations, educational and health practices (Chibvongodze, 2016; Le Grange, 2012; Lefa, 2015; Qobo & Nyathi, 2016). Origin: Sub-Saharan Africa.

Ukama: A term from the Shona people that represents an ethic of relationality and care for all that exists. It acknowledges human interrelatedness in a network of mutuality with all things in the cosmos (Ndofirepi & Shanyanana, 2016). Origin: Southern Africa.

Underlying causes: The deep-rooted social and cultural patterns that shape and reinforce the indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity loss and nature's decline. This assessment highlights what underlies current modes of social organisation and ways of interacting with nature that are causing the multi-layered socio-environmental degradation associated with the polycrisis. This assessment identifies the following underlying causes: disconnection from and domination over nature and people; concentration of power and wealth; and prioritization of short-term, individual and material gains. These underlying causes are not isolated variables but have historically co-evolved and they continue to enforce each other to have far-reaching and systemic impacts (**Chapter 1**).

V

Value, values: Values reflect life goals, beliefs and general guiding principles. They also reflect the opinions or judgements of the importance of specific things in particular situations and contexts. When considering the values of nature, values can refer to nature itself, how nature contributes to people's quality of life, in addition to the way people express the value of life-supporting

processes, functions and systems - interrelating biophysical, spiritual, or symbolic aspects. As in the IPBES Values Assessment, we refer to broad, specific values and value indicators; as well as to instrumental, intrinsic and relational values (IPBES, 2022b).

Value-action gap: Instances wherein consumers do not behave or act in accordance with their beliefs about the environment (Franco & Ghisetti, 2022).

Value chains: the full range of activities that firms and workers do to bring a product from its conception to its end use and beyond (Gereffi & Fernandez-Stark, 2011).

Vested interests: Special benefits enjoyed based on existing economic, political, or social privileges. Vested interests arise because certain people and groups benefit from what businesses and institutions do or make possible—for example, through the services they provide, the supplies they purchase, or the jobs they fund (Moe, 2015).

Views: In this assessment, views refer to the ways of seeing, thinking, or knowing. Views include values of nature, as well as views on legitimacy of knowledge types and around intent and purpose (**Chapter 1**).

Vision: A desirable future (an endpoint in time). Visions usually consist of statements depicting the explicit desires, assumptions, beliefs and paradigms that underlie the desired future (IPBES, 2018b). In this assessment, visions refer to descriptions of desirable future states of nature and people. They are shaped by values and worldviews and often include defined goals and intentional efforts to attain future states (**Chapter 2**).

Visioning: Process of creating a vision, a representation of a desirable future state, which can be operationalized in specific qualitative and quantitative goals and targets, or be more general (Wiek & Lang, 2016).

W

Waka Taurua: Translated as "Double Canoe", this conceptual framework symbolizes the unity of Western and Māori knowledges, characterized as two canoes lashed together, each maintaining its distinct values and perspectives while striving for a common goal (Maxwell *et al.*, 2020). Origin: Maori, New Zealand.

Warinyi: Among the speakers of the *Warumungu* language in Australia, habitat-based classification is expressed through the suffix *warinyi*. This designation has implications for interactions and relationships between humans and other-than-human beings, since, according to this worldview, all "dwellers" of a particular habitat (e.g., plants, animals, humans, etc.) have equal rights (IPBES, 2022b). Origin: Warumungu, Australia.

Whakapapa: Refers to a type of cultural connectedness that encompasses both ancestry and nature and determines both the relationships and obligations that exist for Maori people, who see themselves living within the natural world rather than separate. *Ko au te awa, ko te awa ko au* is a Maori saying that translates to 'I am the river and the river is me' (Charpleix, 2018). Origin: Maori, New Zealand.

Whakatauki: '*Kia whakatōmuri te haere ki whakamua*' (in Maori), To walk into the future our eyes must be fixed on the past (**Chapter 2**). Origin: Maori, New Zealand.

Well-being: The value that someone attaches to personal circumstances in a social state of affairs (Dasgupta, 2001).

Worldviews: Overarching systems of meaning and meaning making that significantly extend inform and influence how humans interpret, enact and co-create reality (Hedlund-de Witt, 2013). Also considered mental lenses through which human social groups perceive, think about, interpret, inhabit and modify the world. Rooted in cultural traditions, they shape and are shaped by knowledge systems, languages and values. Epistemic worldviews pertain to diverse knowledge systems that hold often implicit philosophical assumptions about how nature and values can be known, while human-nature worldviews guide perspectives on our conceptualization of and relationship with nature based on underlying value systems (IPBES, 2022b).

Y

Yindyamarra: A vital term for the Wiradjuri people that is often translated as respect and informs a way of life grounded in mutual respect and caring for all, including self, community, ancestors, land, animals etc. (Sullivan *et al.*, 2016). Origin: Wiradjuri, Australia.

GLOSSARY REFERENCES

- Abson, D. J., Fischer, J., Leventon, J., Newig, J., Schomerus, T., Vilsmaier, U., von Wehrden, H., Abernethy, P., Ives, C. D., Jager, N. W., & Lang, D. J. (2017). Leverage points for sustainability transformation. *Ambio*, 46(1), 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-016-0800-y>
- Acosta, A. (2013). Extractivism and neoextractivism: Two sides of the same curse. *Beyond Development: Alternative Visions from Latin America*, 1, 61–86.
- Agyeman, J., Schlosberg, D., Craven, L., & Matthews, C. (2016). Trends and directions in environmental justice: From inequity to everyday life, community, and just sustainabilities. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 41(1), 321–340. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-110615-090052>
- Albó, X. (2018). Suma Qamaña or Living Well Together: A Contribution to Biocultural Conservation. In R. Rozzi, R. H. May, F. S. Chapin III, F. Massardo, M. C. Gavin, I. J. Klaver, A. Pauchard, M. A. Nuñez, & D. Simberloff (Eds.), *From Biocultural Homogenization to Biocultural Conservation* (Vol. 3, pp. 333–342). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99513-7_21
- Alvaredo, F., Chancel, L., Piketty, T., Saez, E., & Zucman, G. (2018). *World Inequality Report 2018*. Harvard University Press. <https://wid.world/www-site/uploads/2021/01/wir2018-full-report-english-1.pdf>
- Alves, F., Costa, P. M., Novelli, L., & Vidal, D. G. (2023). The rights of nature and the human right to nature: An overview of the European legal system and challenges for the ecological transition. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1175143>
- Angelstam, P., Andersson, K., Annerstedt, M., Axelsson, R., Elbakidze, M., Garrido, P., Grahn, P., Jönsson, K. I., Pedersen, S., Schlyter, P., Skärbäck, E., Smith, M., & Stjernquist, I. (2013). Solving Problems in Social–Ecological Systems: Definition, Practice and Barriers of Transdisciplinary Research. *AMBIO*, 42(2), 254–265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-012-0372-4>
- Arias-Maldonado, M., & Trachtenberg, Z. M. (Eds.). (2019). *Rethinking the environment for the anthropocene: Political theory and sociocultural relations in the new geological epoch*. Routledge.
- Artaraz, K., & Calestani, M. (2015). Suma qamaña in Bolivia: Indigenous Understandings of Well-being and Their Contribution to a Post-Neoliberal Paradigm. *Latin American Perspectives*, 42(5), 216–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582X14547501>
- Avelino, F., & Wittmayer, J. M. (2016). Shifting Power Relations in Sustainability Transitions: A Multi-actor Perspective. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 18(5), 628–649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2015.1112259>
- Ávila, M. B. (2011). The Mayan Indigenous Women of Chiapas: Lekil Kuxlejal and food autonomy. *Development*, 54(4), 485–489. <https://doi.org/10.1057/dev.2011.96>
- Bach, T. (2012). The involvement of agencies in policy formulation: Explaining variation in policy autonomy of federal agencies in Germany. *Policy and Society*, 31(3), 211–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2012.07.003>
- Barth, M., Jiménez-Aceituno, A., Lam, D. P., Bürgener, L., & Lang, D. J. (2023). Transdisciplinary learning as a key leverage for sustainability transformations. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2023.101361>
- Bartlett, C., Marshall, M., & Marshall, A. (2012). Two-Eyed Seeing and other lessons learned within a co-learning journey of bringing together indigenous and mainstream knowledges and ways of knowing. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences* 2012 2:4, 2(4), 331–340. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13412-012-0086-8>
- Batlialwa, S. (1994). The meaning of women's empowerment: New concepts from action. In *Population policies reconsidered: Health, empowerment and rights* (Vol. 17, pp. 127–138). Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press. https://catalog.nlm.nih.gov/discovery/fulldisplay?context=L&vid=01NLM_INST:01NLM_INST&search_scope=MyInstitution&tab=LibraryCatalog&docid=alma9910617553406676
- Bear, C. (2017). Socio-Nature. In *International Encyclopedia of Geography* (pp. 1–5). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118786352.wbieg0212>
- Belk, R. W. (1985). Materialism: Trait aspects of living in the material world. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 12(3), 265–280. <https://doi.org/10.1086/208515>
- Benhabib, S. (2002). *The claims of culture: Equality and diversity in the global era*. Princeton Univ. Press. <https://press.princeton.edu/books/paperback/9780691048635/the-claims-of-culture?srsId=AfmBOopW6B95BkAtaBVQYPLXWxkvJOU7KT2ZrDI50IX-3cp3bk-TxWv>
- Berbés-Blázquez, M., González, J. A., & Pascual, U. (2016). Towards an ecosystem services approach that addresses social power relations. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 19, 134–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2016.02.003>
- Biermann, F., & Gupta, A. (2011). Accountability and legitimacy in earth system governance: A research framework. *Ecological Economics*, 70(11), 1856–1864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.04.008>
- Bischoping, K., & Gazso, A. (2015). *Analyzing talk in the social sciences: Narrative, conversation and discourse strategies*. Sage. <https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/analyzing-talk-in-the-social-sciences/book240935>
- Blok, A., Nakazora, M., & Winthereik, B. R. (2016). Infrastructuring Environments. *Science as Culture*, 25(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09505431.2015.1081500>
- Bloom, P. (2017). The Ethics of Neoliberalism—The Business of Making Capitalism Moral. In *The ethics of neoliberalism: The business of making*

- capitalism moral* (1st Edition). Taylor & Francis. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/mono/10.4324/9781315619019-9/ethics-neoliberalism-peter-bloom?context=ubx&refId=da766abe-687a-46cc-b900-866f65fd634a>
- Blythe, J., Silver, J., Evans, L., Armitage, D., Bennett, N. J., Moore, M., Morrison, T. H., & Brown, K. (2018). The Dark Side of Transformation: Latent Risks in Contemporary Sustainability Discourse. *Antipode*, 50(5), 1206–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12405>
- Bommarco, R., Kleijn, D., & Potts, S. G. (2013). Ecological intensification: Harnessing ecosystem services for food security. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 28(4), 230–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2012.10.012>
- Brahmana, R. K., & Kontesa, M. (2021). Does clean technology weaken the environmental impact on the financial performance? Insight from global oil and gas companies. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(7), 3411–3423. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2810>
- Bullard, R. D. (2001). Environmental Justice in the 21st Century: Race Still Matters. *Phylon* (1960-), 49(3/4), 151–171. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3132626>
- Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme. (2012). *Guidance Notes to the Standard on Biodiversity Offsets*. http://bbop.forest-trends.org/guidelines/Standard_Guidance_Notes.pdf
- Caïra, O., & Schaeffer, J.-M. (2011). *Définir la fiction. Du roman au jeu d'échecs* (Vol. 27). Éditions de l'École des hautes études en sciences sociales. <https://www.calameo.com/read/0009116253f0ea9e2f493>
- Caruso, E., & Sarmiento Barletti, J. P. (2019). Kametsa Asaike. In *Pluriverse: A Post-Development Dictionary*. (pp. 220–223). Columbia University Press. <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/112717>
- Celermajer, D., Chatterjee, S., Cochrane, A., Fishel, S., Neimanis, A., O'Brien, A., Reid, S., Srinivasan, K., Schlosberg, D., & Waldow, A. (2020). Justice through a multispecies lens. *Contemporary Political Theory*, 19, 475–512. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41296-020-00386-5>
- Chaffin, B., Gosnell, H., & Cosens, B. (2014). A decade of adaptive governance scholarship: Synthesis and future directions. *Ecology and Society*, 19(3). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-06824-190356>
- Charpleix, L. (2018). The Whanganui River as Te Awa Tupua: Place-based law in a legally pluralistic society. *The Geographical Journal*, 184(1), 19–30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12238>
- Chibvongodze, D. T. (2016). Ubuntu is Not Only about the Human! An Analysis of the Role of African Philosophy and Ethics in Environment Management. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 53(2), 157–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09709274.2016.11906968>
- Convention on Biological Diversity. (2022). *Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* (No. CBD/COP/15/L.25). Convention on Biological Diversity. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>
- Cook, K. S., & Hegtvedt, K. A. (1983). Distributive Justice, Equity, and Equality. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 9(Volume 9, 1983), 217–241. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.so.09.080183.001245>
- Daly, H. (1972). In Defense of a Steady-State Economy. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 54(5), 945–954. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1239248>
- Dasgupta, P. (2001). The Notion of Well-Being. In P. Dasgupta (Ed.), *Human Well-Being and the Natural Environment*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/0199247889.003.0002>
- Davis, J. L., Green, J. D., & Reed, A. (2009). Interdependence with the environment: Commitment, interconnectedness, and environmental behavior. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 29(2), 173–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2008.11.001>
- de Kalbermatten, G. (2003). *The third advent* (1st U.S. ed). daisyamerica LLC.
- Della Porta & Diani. (2020). Welfare e conflitti sociali. *Parolechiave*, 2, 101–110. <https://doi.org/10.7377/100539>
- Delorme, D., Calidori, N., & Frigo, G. (2024). Ecological Virtuous Selves: Towards a Non-Anthropocentric Environmental Virtue Ethic? *Philosophies*, 9(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/philosophies9010011>
- Deringil, S. (2003). "They Live in a State of Nomadism and Savagery": The Late Ottoman Empire and the Post-Colonial Debate. *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 45(02). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S001041750300015X>
- Deutz, A., Heal, G., Niu, R., Swanson, E., Townshend, T., Li, Z., Delmar, A., Meghji, A., A. Sethi, S., & Tobin de la Puente, J. (2020). *Financing Nature: Closing the global biodiversity financing gap*. The Paulson Institute, The Nature Conservancy, and the Cornell Atkinson Center for Sustainability. https://www.paulsoninstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/FINANCING-NATURE_Full-Report_Final-Version_091520.pdf
- Dijk, P. T. A. van. (1997). *Discourse as Structure and Process*. SAGE.
- Dorninger, C., Hornborg, A., Abson, D. J., Von Wehrden, H., Schaffartzik, A., Giljum, S., Engler, J.-O., Feller, R. L., Hubacek, K., & Wieland, H. (2021). Global patterns of ecologically unequal exchange: Implications for sustainability in the 21st century. *Ecological Economics*, 179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106824>
- Dubuisson-Quellier, S., & Plessz, M. (2013). La théorie des pratiques. *Sociologie*, N°4, vol. 4. <https://journals.openedition.org/sociologie/2030>
- Dworkin. (2001). What is Equality? Part 1: Equality of Welfare. In *The Notion of Equality* (pp. 81–142). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315199795-6>
- EHNE. (n.d.). *Extractivism and environment in Europe (sixteenth–twenty-first century)*. Retrieved 14 June 2024, from <https://ehne.fr/en/encyclopedia/themes/ecology-and-environment-in-europe/mobilizing-energies/extractivism-and-environment-in-europe-sixteenth%E2%80%93twenty-first-century>
- Endangered Languages Project. (n.d.). Retrieved 14 June 2024, from https://www.endangeredlanguages.com/about_importance/
- ESMA. (2024). *Final Report on Greenwashing*. https://www.esma.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-06/ESMA36-287652198-2699_Final_Report_on_Greenwashing.pdf

- European Environment Agency. (n.d.). *Business as usual scenario* [Term]. European Environment Agency. Retrieved 17 June 2024, from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/help/glossary/eea-glossary/business-as-usual-scenario>
- Fang, F., Kang, S.-P., & Liu, S. (2004). Measuring Mindset Change in the Systemic Transformation of Education. In *Association for Educational Communications and Technology*. Association for Educational Communications and Technology. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED484992>
- FAO. (2018). *Sustainable food systems: Concept and framework*. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/b620989c-407b-4caf-a152-f790f55fec71/content>
- Fischer, J., Farny, S., Abson, D. J., Zuin Zeidler, V., Von Salisch, M., Schaltegger, S., Martín-López, B., Temperton, V. M., & Kümmeler, K. (2024). Mainstreaming regenerative dynamics for sustainability. *Nature Sustainability*, 7(8), 964–972. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01368-w>
- Fischer, J., & Riechers, M. (2019). A leverage points perspective on sustainability. *People and Nature*, 1(1), 115–120. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.13>
- Font Vivanco, D., McDowall, W., Freire-González, J., Kemp, R., & van der Voet, E. (2016). The foundations of the environmental rebound effect and its contribution towards a general framework. *Ecological Economics*, 125(C), 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2016.02.006>
- Foster, J. B. (1999). Marx's Theory of Metabolic Rift: Classical Foundations for Environmental Sociology. *American Journal of Sociology*, 105(2), 366–405. <https://doi.org/10.1086/210315>
- Franco, C., & Ghisetti, C. (2022). What shapes the “value-action” gap? The role of time perception reconsidered. *Economia Politica*, 39(3), 1023–1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40888-022-00282-8>
- Geels, F. W. (2011). The multi-level perspective on sustainability transitions: Responses to seven criticisms. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 1(1), 24–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2011.02.002>
- Gereffi, G., & Fernandez-Stark, K. (2011). *Global Value Chain Analysis: A Primer*. https://www.globalvaluechains.org/wp-content/uploads/Primer_1stEd_2011.pdf
- Gliessman, S., & Titonell, P. (2015). Agroecology for Food Security and Nutrition. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*, 39(2), 131–133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683565.2014.972001>
- Goldstein, J. E., Neimark, B., Garvey, B., & Phelps, J. (2023). Unlocking “lock-in” and path dependency: A review across disciplines and socio-environmental contexts. *World Development*, 161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2022.106116>
- Goralnik & Nelson. (2012). *Anthropocentrism*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.1777.6324>
- Gordon, E., Davila, F., & Riedy, C. (2023). Regenerative agriculture: A potentially transformative storyline shared by nine discourses. *Sustainability Science*, 18(4), 1833–1849. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01281-1>
- Gorenflo, L. J., Romaine, S., Mittermeier, R. A., & Walker-Painemilla, K. (2012). Co-occurrence of linguistic and biological diversity in biodiversity hotspots and high biodiversity wilderness areas. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 109(21), 8032–8037. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1117511109>
- Grosfoguel, R. (2016). What is Racism? *Journal of World-Systems Research*, 22(1), 9–15. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jwsr.2016.609>
- Haas, P. (1992). *Knowledge, Power, and International Policy Coordination*. MIT Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/i327218>
- Hakkarainen, V., Mäkinen-Rostedt, K., Horcea-Milcu, A., D'Amato, D., Jämsä, J., & Soini, K. (2022). Transdisciplinary research in natural resources management: Towards an integrative and transformative use of co-concepts. *Sustainable Development*, 30(2), 309–325. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2276>
- Harris, N., & Delanty, G. (2023). What is capitalism? Toward a working definition. *Social Science Information*, 62(3), 323–344. <https://doi.org/10.1177/05390184231203878>
- Harrison, K. D. (2008). *When languages die: The extinction of the world's languages and the erosion of human knowledge* (1. issued as paperback). Oxford University Press.
- Hasse, R. (2019). Chapter 2. What Difference Does it Make? An Institutional Perspective on Actors and Types Thereof. In H. Hwang, J. A. Colyvas, & G. S. Drori (Eds.), *Research in the Sociology of Organizations* (Vol. 58, pp. 23–41). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S0733-558X20190000058004>
- Hayashi, D. (2020). Harnessing innovation policy for industrial decarbonization: Capabilities and manufacturing in the wind and solar power sectors of China and India. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101644>
- Hedlund-de Witt, A. (2013). Worldviews and Their Significance for the Global Sustainable Development Debate. *Environmental Ethics*, 35(2), 133–162. <https://doi.org/10.5840/enviroethics201335215>
- Henderson, D. (2002). Norms, Normative Principles, and Explanation: On Not Getting Is from Ought. *Philosophy of the Social Sciences*, 32(3), 329–364. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004839310203200303>
- Higgins, P., Short, D., & South, N. (2013). Protecting the planet: A proposal for a law of ecocide. *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 59(3), 251–266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10611-013-9413-6>
- Hill, P. C., Pargament, K. I., Hood, R. W., McCullough, M. E., Swyers, J. P., Larson, D. B., & Zinnbauer, B. J. (2000). Conceptualizing religion and spirituality: Points of commonality, points of departure. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 30(1), 51–77. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-5914.00119>
- Hjeij, M., & Vilks, A. (2023). A brief history of heuristics: How did research on heuristics evolve? *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 64. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01542-z>
- Holland, R. (1999). Reflexivity. *Human Relations*, 52(4), 463–484. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872679905200403>
- Hornborg, A. (1998). Towards an ecological theory of unequal exchange: Articulating world system theory and ecological

- economics. *Ecological Economics*, 25(1), 127–136. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009\(97\)00100-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009(97)00100-6)
- Hornborg, A. (2014). Ecological economics, Marxism, and technological progress: Some explorations of the conceptual foundations of theories of ecologically unequal exchange. *Ecological Economics*, 105, 11–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.05.015>
- Hornborg, A., & Martinez-Alier, J. (2016). Ecologically unequal exchange and ecological debt. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 23(1), 328–333. <https://doi.org/10.2458/v23i1.20220>
- Hou, Y. (2019). Hurai. In A. Kothari, A. Salleh, A. Escobar, F. Demaria, & A. Acosta, *Pluriverse: A Post-Development Dictionary*. Tulika Books.
- Huntjens, P., Rinscheid, A., Kemp, R., Helvoirt, B. V., Aarts, N., Visseren-Hamakers, I., Veen, A. van, & Hassink, J. (2023). *The Transformation Flower Approach for Leveraging Change Towards Multiple Value Creation and Institutional Change*. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202307.1539.v1>
- ICCA Consortium. (2021). *Territories of Life*. <https://report.territoriesoflife.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/ICCA-Territories-of-Life-2021-Report-FULL-150dpi-ENG.pdf>
- Ikeme, J. (2003). Equity, environmental justice and sustainability: Incomplete approaches in climate change politics. *Global Environmental Change*, 13(3), 195–206. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780\(03\)00047-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780(03)00047-5)
- Ingold, K., Moser, A., Metz, F., Herzog, L., Bader, H.-P., Scheidegger, R., & Stamm, C. (2018). Misfit between physical affectedness and regulatory embeddedness: The case of drinking water supply along the Rhine River. *Global Environmental Change*, 48, 136–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.11.006>
- International Decade of Indigenous Languages 2022 – 2032 | United Nations For Indigenous Peoples*. (n.d.). Retrieved 15 September 2023, from <https://www.un.org/development/desa/indigenouseoples/indigenous-languages.html>
- IPBES. (2016). *The assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services on pollinators, pollination and food production*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3402856>
- IPBES. (2018a). *The IPBES assessment report on land degradation and restoration*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237393>
- IPBES. (2018b). *The IPBES regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Europe and Central Asia*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237429>
- IPBES. (2019a). *Global assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6417333>
- IPBES. (2019b). *Report of the second ILK dialogue workshop the IPBES assessment of the diverse conceptualisations of multiple values of nature: Reviewing the first order draft*. IPBES. https://files.ipbes.net/ipbes-web-prod-public-files/inline-files/IPBES_Values_2ndILKDialogue_Report_final_ForWeb.pdf
- IPBES. (2021). *IPBES Core Glossary*. <https://ipbes.net/node/16454>
- IPBES. (2022a). *Annex I: Glossary of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7157888>
- IPBES. (2022b). *Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522522>
- IPBES. (2022c). *Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448567>
- IPBES. (2023). *Report of the third Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop on the IPBES assessment of transformative change: Reviewing the first draft of the summary for policymakers and second drafts of the chapters*. IPBES.
- IPBES. (2024). *Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (P. A. Harrison, P. D. McElwee, & T. L. van Huysen, Eds.). IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850054>
- IPCC. (n.d.). *Glossary*. Retrieved 20 September 2023, from <https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/>
- IPCC. (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E. S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, & B. Rama, Eds.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844>
- IUCN. (2021). *Biodiversity offsets*. <https://www.iucn.org/resources/issues-brief/biodiversity-offsets>
- Jouffray, J.-B., Blasiak, R., Norström, A. V., Österblom, H., & Nyström, M. (2020). The Blue Acceleration: The Trajectory of Human Expansion into the Ocean. *One Earth*, 2(1), 43–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.12.016>
- Kaliappan, A., Hamid, H., & Madar, A. R. (2023). Experts' Opinion Matters! Green Technology Elements for Construction Technology in Vocational Colleges. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 15(1), 167–177. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30880/jtet.2023.15.01.015>
- Kemp, R., Weaver, P. M., Strasser, T., Backhaus, J., & Golland, A. (2018). Socio-economic transformations: Insights for sustainability. In *Perspectives on Transitions to Sustainability* (pp. 70–96). European Environment Agency, European Commission. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/perspectives-on-transitions-to-sustainability>
- Kersten, A., & Shivakumar, S. (2022). *Rethinking Shareholder Primacy in the New Innovation Economy*. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/rethinking-shareholder-primacy-new-innovation-economy>

- Kimmerer, R. (2014). Returning the gift. *Minding Nature*, 7(2), 18–24.
- Kivimaa, P., Laakso, S., Lonkila, A., & Kaljonen, M. (2021). Moving beyond disruptive innovation: A review of disruption in sustainability transitions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 38, 110–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2020.12.001>
- Kothari, A., Saleh, A., Escobar, A., Demaria, F., & Acosta, A. (Eds.). (2019). *Pluriverse: A post-development dictionary*. Tulika Books and Authorsupfront.
- Kramer, K.-L. (2012). *User Experience in the Age of Sustainability: A Practitioner's Blueprint*. Elsevier.
- Lane, J. P. (1999). Understanding Technology Transfer. *Assistive Technology*, 11(1), 5–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400435.1999.10131981>
- Lawrence, M. G., Williams, S., Nanz, P., & Renn, O. (2022). Characteristics, potentials, and challenges of transdisciplinary research. *One Earth*, 5(1), 44–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.12.010>
- Le Grange, L. (2012). Ubuntu, ukama, environment and moral education. *Journal of Moral Education*, 41(3), 329–340. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2012.691631>
- Lefa, B. J. (2015). *The African Philosophy of Ubuntu in South African Education*. <https://www.studocu.com/en-za/document/varsity-college/jurisprudence/the-african-philosophy-of-ubuntu-in-south-african-education/92102134>
- Levidow, L., & Papaioannou, T. (2018). Which inclusive innovation? Competing normative assumptions around social justice. *Innovation and Development*, 8(2), 209–226. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2157930X.2017.1351605>
- Lindgren, T. (2018). Ecocide, genocide and the disregard of alternative life-systems. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 22(4), 525–549. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642987.2017.1397631>
- Lukes, S. (2005). *Power: A radical view* (2nd ed.). Palgrave Macmillan. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41802305>
- Ma, K., & Wei, F. (2021). Ecological civilization: A revived perspective on the relationship between humanity and nature. *National Science Review*, 8(7). <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwab112>
- Maffi, L. (2007). *The SAGE Handbook of Environment and Society*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848607873>
- Mason, M. (2008). The Governance of Transnational Environmental Harm: Addressing New Modes of Accountability/Responsibility. *Global Environmental Politics*, 8(3), 8–24. <https://doi.org/10.1162/glep.2008.8.3.8>
- Mausser, W., Klepper, G., Rice, M., Schmalzbauer, B. S., Hackmann, H., Leemans, R., & Moore, H. (2013). Transdisciplinary global change research: The co-creation of knowledge for sustainability. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 5(3–4), 420–431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.07.001>
- Maxwell, K., Awatere, S., Ratana, K., Davies, K., & Taiaapa, C. (2020). He waka eke noa/we are all in the same boat: A framework for co-governance from aotearoa New Zealand. *Marine Policy*, 121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104213>
- Meadows, D. H. (1999). *Leverage points: Places to intervene in a system*. Academy for Systems Change. <http://donellameadows.org/archives/leverage-points-places-to-intervene-in-a-system/>
- Meadows, D. H. (2008). *Thinking in Systems: International Bestseller*. Chelsea Green Publishing.
- Mezirow, J. (1997). Transformative Learning: Theory to Practice. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 1997(74), 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.7401>
- Milanovic, B. (2011). A short history of global inequality: The past two centuries. *Explorations in Economic History*, 48(4), 494–506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eeh.2011.05.001>
- Milkoreit, M., Hodbod, J., Baggio, J., Benessaiah, K., Calderón-Contreras, R., Donges, J. F., Mathias, J.-D., Rocha, J. C., Schoon, M., & Werners, S. E. (2018). Defining tipping points for social-ecological systems scholarship—An interdisciplinary literature review. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(3), 033005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaa75>
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (Ed.). (2005). *Ecosystems and human well-being: Synthesis; a report of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment*. Island Press. <https://edepot.wur.nl/45159>
- Misa, T. J., Brey, P., & Feenberg, A. (2003). *Modernity and Technology*. MIT Press.
- Mitchell, S. (2018). *Sacred instructions: Indigenous wisdom for living spirit-based change*. North Atlantic Books.
- Moe, T. M. (2015). Vested Interests and Political Institutions. *Political Science Quarterly*, 130(2), 277–318. <https://doi.org/10.1002/polq.12321>
- Moore, M.-L., Riddell, D., & Vocisano, D. (2015). Scaling Out, Scaling Up, Scaling Deep: Strategies of Non-profits in Advancing Systemic Social Innovation. *Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 2015(58), 67–84. <https://doi.org/10.9774/GLEAF.4700.2015.ju.00009>
- Muller, S. D., Miramont, C., Bruneton, H., Carre, M., Sottocornola, M., Court-Picon, M., de Beaulieu, J.-L., Nakagawa, T., & Schevin, P. (2012). A palaeoecological perspective for the conservation and restoration of wetland plant communities in the central French Alps, with particular emphasis on alder carr vegetation. *Review of palaeobotany and palynology*, 171, 124–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.revpalbo.2011.12.005>
- Murrey, A. (2020). Colonialism. In *International Encyclopedia of Human Geography* (pp. 315–326). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102295-5.10804-2>
- Nash, C. J. (2009). Patriarchy. In *International Encyclopedia of Human Geography* (pp. 102–107). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08044910-4.00982-2>
- Ndofirepi, A. P., & Shanyana, R. N. (2016). Rethinking *ukama* in the context of 'Philosophy for Children' in Africa. *Research Papers in Education*, 31(4), 428–441. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2015.1073773>

- North, D. C. (1991). Institutions. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 5(1), 97–112. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.5.1.97>
- Novak, M. (2000). Defining Social Justice. *First Things*. <https://www.firstthings.com/article/2000/12/defining-social-justice>
- O'Brien, K. (2018). Is the 1.5°C target possible? Exploring the three spheres of transformation. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 31, 153–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.04.010>
- OECD. (2013). *Innovation and Inclusive Development. Discussion Report from 2012 Conference*. <https://web-archiv.oecd.org/2013-02-27/216206-oecd-inclusive-innovation.pdf>
- Otto, I. M., Wiedermann, M., Cremades, R., Donges, J. F., Auer, C., & Lucht, W. (2020). Human agency in the Anthropocene. *Ecological Economics*, 167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106463>
- Pascual, U., Adams, W. M., Díaz, S., Lele, S., Mace, G. M., & Turnhout, E. (2021). Biodiversity and the challenge of pluralism. *Nature Sustainability*, 4(7), 567–572. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-021-00694-7>
- Porpora, D. V. (1989). Four Concepts of Social Structure. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 19(2), 195–211. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5914.1989.tb00144.x>
- Pörtner, H.-O., Scholes, R. J., Agard, J., Archer, E., Arneeth, A., Bai, X., Barnes, D., Burrows, M., Chan, L., Cheung, W. L. (William), Diamond, S., Donatti, C., Duarte, C., Eisenhauer, N., Foden, W., Gasalla, M. A., Handa, C., Hickler, T., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., ... Ngo, H. (2021). *Scientific outcome of the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop on biodiversity and climate change* (Version 5). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4659158>
- Puig de la Bellacasa, M. (2017). *Matters of care: Speculative ethics in more than human worlds*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Qobo, M., & Nyathi, N. (2016). Ubuntu, public policy ethics and tensions in South Africa's foreign policy. *South African Journal of International Affairs*, 23(4), 421–436. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10220461.2017.1298052>
- Quijano, A. (2007). Coloniality and Modernity/Rationality. *Cultural Studies*, 21(2–3), 168–178. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502380601164353>
- Rachels, S., & Rachels, J. (2015). *The elements of moral philosophy* (8. ed). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Rakowski, E. (1991). *Equal Justice*. Clarendon Press.
- Raskin, P. D. (2005). Global scenarios: Background review for the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. *Ecosystems*, 8(2), 133–142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-004-0074-2>
- Rawls, J. (2020). *A Theory of Justice: Revised Edition*. Harvard University Press.
- Rayner, S., & Malone, E. L. (2001). Climate change, poverty, and intragenerational equity: The national level. *International Journal of Global Environmental Issues*, 1(2), 175–202. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/IJGENVI.2001.000977>
- Reid, A. J., Eckert, L. E., Lane, J., Young, N., Hinch, S. G., Darimont, C. T., Cooke, S. J., Ban, N. C., & Marshall, A. (2020). "Two-Eyed Seeing": An Indigenous framework to transform fisheries research and management. *Fish and Fisheries*, 22(2), 243–261. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12516>
- Robinson, J. (2004). Squaring the circle? Some thoughts on the idea of sustainable development. *Ecological Economics*, 48(4), 369–384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2003.10.017>
- Robson, G. J., & Tsou, J. Y. (2023). *Technology Ethics: A Philosophical Introduction and Readings*. Taylor & Francis.
- Rodriguez-Gonzalez, P. T., Rico-Martinez, R., & Rico-Ramirez, V. (2020). Effect of feedback loops on the sustainability and resilience of human-ecosystems. *Ecological Modelling*, 426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2020.109018>
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations, 5th Edition*. Simon and Schuster.
- Rook, L. (2013). Mental models: A robust definition. *The Learning Organization*, 20(1), 38–47. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09696471311288519>
- Rybråten, S., Aira, H., Andersen, S., Joks, S., & Nilsen, S. (2024). Mijå duobddága: Sankingspraksiser i samiske kystområder – relasjoner, verdier og bærekraft. *Tidsskrift for Samfunnsforskning*, 65(1), 46–61. <https://doi.org/10.18261/tfs.65.1.3>
- Salmón, E. (2000). Kincentric Ecology: Indigenous Perceptions of the Human–Nature Relationship. *Ecological Applications*, 10(5), 1327–1332. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(2000\)010\[1327:KEIPOT\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(2000)010[1327:KEIPOT]2.0.CO;2)
- Salzman, P. C. (2002). On Reflexivity. *American Anthropologist*, 104(3), 805–811. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.2002.104.3.805>
- Sands, P., Sow, D. F., Kate Mackintosh, Richard J Rogers, Valérie Cabanes, Pablo Fajardo, Syeda Rizwana Hasan, Charles C Jalloh, Rodrigo Lledó, Tuiloma Neroni Slade, Christina Voigt, Alex Whiting, & Jojo Mehta. (2021, June). *Independent Expert Panel for the Legal Definition of Ecocide—Commentary and core text*. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5ca2608ab914493c64ef1f6d/t/60d1e6e604fae2201d03407f/1624368879048/SE+Foundation+Commentary+and+core+text+rev+6.pdf>
- Santika, T., Nelson, V., Flint, M., MacEwen, M., Cerretelli, S., & Brack, D. (2024). Leverage points for tackling unsustainable global value chains: Market-based measures versus transformative alternatives. *Sustainability Science*, 19(1), 285–305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01430-0>
- Sara, M. N. (2001). *Reinen - et gode fra vinden: Reindriftens tilpasningsformer i Kautokeino*. Davvi girji. <https://www.norli.no/boker/fagboker/teknologi-ingenior-og-primaer/landbruk-og-skogbruk/reinen-et-gode-fra-vinden>
- Schot, J., & Steinmueller, W. E. (2018). Three frames for innovation policy: R&D, systems of innovation and transformative change. *Research Policy*, 47(9), 1554–1567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.08.011>
- Sharma, M. (2007). *World Wisdom in Action. Personal to Planetary Transformation*. <https://kosmosjournal.org/wp-content/article-pdfs/personal-to-planetary-transformation.pdf>

- Sherwin, W. (2020, November 20). Socialism: Foundations and Key Concepts. *JSTOR Daily*. <https://daily.jstor.org/reading-list-socialism/>
- Shrivastava, P., Stafford Smith, M., O'Brien, K., & Zsolnai, L. (2020). Transforming Sustainability Science to Generate Positive Social and Environmental Change Globally. *One Earth*, 2(4), 329–340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.04.010>
- Silan, W., & Munkejord, M. C. (2022). Hmali', rrgyax and Gaga: A study of Tayal elders reclaiming their Indigenous identities in Taiwan. *AlterNative: An International Journal of Indigenous Peoples*, 18(3), 354–363. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11771801221119214>
- Singh, A. (2014). Ecological consciousness in Jainism: Exploring realities, constraints, and traditions. *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, 75. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44158361>
- Smith, L. T. (1999). *Decolonizing Methodologies. Research and Indigenous Peoples*. Zed Books.
- Steup, M., & Neta, R. (2005). *Epistemology*. https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/epistemology/?utm_medium=podcast&utm_source=bc&utm_campaign=gold-exchange-with-keith-weiner
- Stinchcombe, A. (2015). Social structure and organizations. In J. G. March (Ed.), *Handbook of organizations* (pp. 142–193). Routledge.
- Stirling, A. (2019). Engineering and Sustainability: Control and Care in Unfoldings of Modernity. *SPRU Working Paper Series*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3336826>
- Stirling, A. (2023). Against misleading technocratic precision in research evaluation and wider policy – A response to Franzoni and Stephan (2023), 'uncertainty and risk-taking in science'. *Research Policy*, 52(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2022.104709>
- Sullivan, B., Grant, S., & Grant, A. F. (2016). *Yindymarra Yambuwan: Respecting everything*. Sharing & Learning.
- Takács-Sánta, A. (2022). Clarifying the driving forces behind our ecological crisis: A general model. *Biologia Futura*, 73(4), 405–410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42977-022-00137-0>
- Tan, E. C. D., & Lamers, P. (2021). Circular Bioeconomy Concepts—A Perspective. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FRSUS.2021.701509/BIBTEX>
- The Lancet Planetary Health. (2017). Welcome to The Lancet Planetary Health. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 1(1). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(17\)30013-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(17)30013-X)
- Tittonell, P., El Mujtar, V., Felix, G., Kebede, Y., Laborda, L., Luján Soto, R., & De Vente, J. (2022). Regenerative agriculture—Agroecology without politics? *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2022.844261>
- Turchin, P. (2003). *Complex Population Dynamics*. <https://press.princeton.edu/books/paperback/9780691090214/complex-population-dynamics>
- UNEP. (2017). *International Resource Panel Glossary*. <https://www.resourcepanel.org/glossary>
- UNEP. (2022). *Nature-based solutions for supporting sustainable development* (No. UNEP/EA.5/Res.5). file:///C:/Users/renaud/Downloads/UNEP_EA.5_RES.5-EN.pdf
- UNEP. (2024). *Navigating New Horizons: A global foresight report on planetary health and human wellbeing*. <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/45890>
- United Nations. (1948). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/UDHR/Documents/UDHR_Translations/eng.pdf
- United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development* (No. A/RES/70/1; p. 41). United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.1891/9780826190123.ap02>
- UNRISD. (2022). *Crises of Inequality: Shifting Power for a New Eco-Social Contract*. United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.18356/9789290851332>
- Vanasupa, L., & Schlemmer, L. T. (2016). Transcending industrial era paradigms: Exploring together the meaning of academic leadership for diversity. *2016 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition*.
- Vasan, S. (2018). Ecological Crisis and the Logic of Capital. *Sociological Bulletin*, 67(3), 275–289.
- Visseren-Hamakers, I. J., & Kok, M. T. J. (2022). The Urgency of Transforming Biodiversity Governance. In I. J. Visseren-Hamakers & M. T. J. Kok (Eds.), *Transforming Biodiversity Governance* (1st ed., pp. 3–22). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108856348.002>
- Visseren-Hamakers, I. J., Razzaque, J., McElwee, P., Turnhout, E., Kelemen, E., Rusch, G. M., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Chan, I., Lim, M., Islar, M., Gautam, A. P., Williams, M., Mungatana, E., Karim, M. S., Muradian, R., Gerber, L. R., Lui, G., Liu, J., Spangenberg, J. H., & Zaleski, D. (2021). Transformative governance of biodiversity: Insights for sustainable development. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 53, 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2021.06.002>
- Voulvoulis, N., Giakoumis, T., Hunt, C., Kioupi, V., Petrou, N., Souliotis, I., Vaghela, C., & Binti Wan Rosely, Wih. (2022). Systems thinking as a paradigm shift for sustainability transformation. *Global Environmental Change*, 75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2022.102544>
- Walker, B., & Salt, D. (2012). *Resilience Thinking: Sustaining Ecosystems and People in a Changing World*. Island Press.
- Wamsler, C., & Osberg, G. (2022). Transformative climate policy mainstreaming – engaging the political and the personal. *Global Sustainability*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2022.11>
- Wamsler, C., Osberg, G., Osika, W., Herndersson, H., & Mundaca, L. (2021). Linking internal and external transformation for sustainability and climate action: Towards a new research and policy agenda. *Global Environmental Change*, 71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102373>
- Warber, S. L., DeHudy, A. A., Bialko, M. F., Marselle, M. R., & Irvine, K. N. (2015). Addressing “nature-deficit disorder”: A mixed methods pilot study of young adults attending a wilderness camp. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/651827>

Watts, V. (2013). Indigenous place-thought & agency amongst humans and non humans (First Woman and Sky Woman go on a European world tour!). *Decolonization : indigeneity, education & society*, 2, 20–34.

West, S., Haider, L. J., Stålhammar, S., & Woroniecki, S. (2020). A relational turn for sustainability science? Relational thinking, leverage points and transformations. *Ecosystems and People*, 16(1), 304–325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2020.1814417>

What Is Greenwashing? (2023, February 9). <https://www.nrdc.org/stories/what-greenwashing>

Wiedmann, T., & Barrett, J. (2010). A Review of the Ecological Footprint Indicator—Perceptions and Methods. *Sustainability*, 2(6), 1645–1693. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su2061645>

Wiek, A., & Lang, D. J. (2016). Transformational sustainability research methodology. *Sustainability Science*:

An Introduction, 31–41. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-7242-6_3

Wong, L., & Bridges, J. F. P. (2008). Consumerism: Overview. In *International Encyclopedia of Public Health* (pp. 1–7). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012373960-5.00574-8>

Wood, E. M. (1972). *Mind and politics. An approach to the meaning of liberal and socialist individualism*. University of California Press.

World Commission on Environment and Development. (1987). *Our Common Future*. Oxford University Press. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-future.pdf>

World Health Organization. (2021). *Health Promotion Glossary of Terms 2021*. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/350161/9789240038349-eng.pdf?sequence=1>

Young, O. (2008). Institutions and Environmental Change: The Scientific Legacy of a Decade of IDGEC Research. In O. Young, L. A. King, & H. Schroeder (Eds.), *Institutions and Environmental Change: Principal Findings, Applications, and Research Frontiers* (pp. 3–46). The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9780262240574.003.0001>

Young, P. (1995). *Equity: In theory and practice* (1. Princeton paperback printing). Princeton University Press.

Ziervogel, G., Cowen, A., & Ziniades, J. (2016). Moving from Adaptive to Transformative Capacity: Building Foundations for Inclusive, Thriving, and Regenerative Urban Settlements. *Sustainability*, 8(9), 955. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8090955>

